

The responsible development of Automated Machine Learning technology in REDD+

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The responsible development of Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) technology in REDD+

Master thesis

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Summary

This thesis is written for the Environmental Policy group at Wageningen University and Research. In this thesis, developments in software technology related to artificial intelligence and machine learning were analysed for their use in REDD+ monitoring, reporting and verification processes.

The REDD+ MRV processes depend on technology in several forms, such as the collection of satellite imagery, the development and use of specialised deforestation detection software and the use of mobile devices to collect ground-samples. In this thesis, the use of a new form of data analysis was researched with standardised software development methods for the creation of new innovations in software. A prototype application was developed to showcase the possibilities of such an innovative technology (called AutoML) in REDD+ MRV processes. With the use of value-sensitive design and responsible innovation software development methods, the development and potential use of machine learning for the use of REDD+ MRV processes was analysed with a prototype application, existing scientific literature and expert interviews. The expert interviews were conducted with experts in machine learning and REDD+.

The results of the research show a clear use-case and potential for automated machine learning technology in REDD+. The technology could be developed to target specific monitoring issues in current REDD+ projects, or could improve upon costs and accuracy in monitoring real-time deforestation. For the creation of automated machine learning models, human interaction, especially with local communities, is required. With those requirements, there is potential for larger community involvement in the MRV processes with the use of AutoML technology.

Ethical concerns related to automated machine learning and big data however need to be carefully considered. For some REDD+ specific issues, such as property rights, no clear path was found for machine learning to improve, but also no path was found to negatively influence these aspects.

Overall, the results of the study show potential possibilities, but also drawbacks of the development of AutoML technology for REDD+ MRV processes. Depending on the development and funding available for REDD+ monitoring tools, the use of AutoML could play a role in the toolbox of future REDD+ monitoring methods.

I. Introduction

Climate change will be one of the biggest challenges for humankind in 21st century. Climate change is threatening ecosystems worldwide, with the UNFCCC predicting massive biodiversity losses, extreme weather events and rising sea levels as alarming developments. With 14% of greenhouse gasses emitted by deforestation, in 2015, a special deforestation prevention program was included in the Paris climate agreement. The program, called REDD (Reduction of Emissions caused by Deforestation and land Degradation), has received billions of funding and is active globally, in over 51 countries and 360 projects (UNFCCC, 2021).

To prevent deforestation, the REDD+ program places a monetary value on the climate effects of a forest. Also referred to as “ecosystem services” a forest provides a service for the Earth’s climate by storing carbon, in soils and in tree material. The loss of forests, deforestation, thus directly leads to higher concentrations of carbon-dioxide (a greenhouse gas) in the atmosphere, resulting in climate change.

Forests are heavily deforested, mainly for the economic value of the soil they stand on. Soil can be used for agriculture, and thus generate economic value. The potential of economic profit from deforestation has led to wide-spread, and rapid, deforestation in the past decades (Rudel et al. 2009). Most of the deforestation happens in developing countries, for which high percentages of the population live below or just above the poverty rate. Preventing deforestation has been proven difficult, mainly due to the economic incentives deforested land provides. In 2005, a conceptual program was developed which tackles deforestation directly at the core of these financial incentives, by providing land owners with direct ecosystem service payments, as a means to prevent them from deforesting their land. The program was called RED (Reduction of Emissions due to Deforestation). The program was expanded from the initial start in 2005, to also cover forest degradation, enhancement of carbon stocks and improved forest protection, hence the extra D and “+”, REDD+ (Angelsen et al. 2018).

REDD+ projects prevent deforestation by substituting potential economic gains of the forest with direct payments to land owners. These payments are related to the ecosystem services the forests provides, *not* the potential agricultural profits. To calculate ecosystem services, like carbon offsets, REDD+ projects use a myriad of monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) processes. With MRV processes, the REDD program uses baseline projections of future deforestation (if no forest protection is undertaken), and compares the actual situation with the baseline projection to calculate prevented amounts of deforestation (Arts et al. 2019).

Problem statement

The basis of REDD+, the operations around which REDD+ projects work, depend on the MRV processes. Therefore, for REDD+ projects to work, there needs to be robust monitoring, reporting and verification methods. Similarly, REDD+ project managers need effective methods to prevent deforestation from happening. More challenging, are the budgetary and technical limitations related to MRV processes. Limited funding is available for robust monitoring solutions. More problematic is that, if robust monitoring solutions are implemented, their costs are sometimes higher than the direct payments made for the actual forest’s ecosystem services (Köhl et al. 2020).

MRV processes use a combination of satellite colour, multispectral photography and ground-sampling methods to monitor forests. These methods heavily depend on software-based programs to calculate deforestation. In the past few years, machine learning technology has

emerged as a powerful tool to analyse data. The technology is used to analyse billions of data points every day. However, in the MRV processes of REDD+, the technology is as of yet not present, with only a very limited selection of published scientific papers or white-papers combining the technology with REDD+.

Resources in environmental monitoring are limited (Köhl et al. 2020), and the development of new software, which would use Machine Learning technology, is expensive. Although computers have become exponentially more powerful in the past years, the development of software is manual labor. The development of Machine Learning software used to require specialized skills and toolsets, and thus also a large amount of financial resources (ITRex, 2021). The difficulty at which Artificial Intelligent (AI) technology like Machine Learning is implemented is however changing rapidly with advancements made with publicly available AI software.

In 2014, the first step towards lowering the entry bar into AI technology was introduced under the name “Automated Machine Learning”, also called AutoML. With AutoML, data in any form can be analyzed with AI, without the need for any programming knowledge. It allows for rapid integration into existing software solutions, and also enables new possibilities with data analysis. AutoML tools require little experience with data analysis, but still provide statistically sound output. Using several algorithms, the tools automate many of the steps machine learning scientists normally undertake when analyzing data, such as selecting the appropriate analysis method and dealing with uncertainties in the analysis. With the technology, non-experts have the ability to perform statistically sound analyses without any programming knowledge or experience with machine learning (Feurer et al. 2015).

With Machine Learning technology, in the past few years, hundreds of innovative new applications have been developed. The technology is used to analyse the climate, bird flight patterns, biodiversity, prevent poaching and more (Tahmasebi et al., 2020). The technology has also been developed in small selection of pilots for forest monitoring, with great success in aspects of accuracy and speed compared to classical methods.

However, so far, none of the AutoML research has had a focus on REDD+, and its monitoring (MRV) processes, which are highly complex and diverse. There is however a need for a new approach in REDD+ monitoring processes, which are highly complex, and thus expensive. It's however unsure how new monitoring technology could assist in the myriad of MRV process difficulties in REDD+ projects.

With the potential of AI technology like AutoML, also come ethical limitations, as there are certain risks and limitations involved with AI applications. Experts have warned about harmful implementations of AI software. AutoML in particular has been scrutinised by security researchers (Kortical, 2021). AutoML technology in general is regarded a “black box” technology as the high complexity of AI models is difficult to fathom. With AutoML, these complex models can be generated by users without any background knowledge of statistics or artificial intelligence. Security researchers have therefore presented concerns related to the ethical and responsible use of the AutoML technology (Google AI, 2020). The ethical concerns surrounding AutoML technology however have not stopped or delayed its implementation. The use of AutoML is skyrocketing among scientific researchers, companies and is evermore integrated into consumer products. It is likely only a matter of time before AutoML is used in environmental monitoring applications like forest monitoring. The responsible development of AutoML for these applications is thus something which needs to be determined at the current stage of development. In this thesis, I will research the responsible future development and potential use of AutoML technology in REDD+.

1.1 Research questions

What are the use-cases of automated machine learning for REDD+ monitoring, reporting and verification processes and how could these use-cases be developed in a responsible way?

Subquestions

1. How could AutoML technology be utilised in REDD+ monitoring, reporting and verification processes?
2. Which software development approaches would be suitable to research the future responsible development of AutoML in REDD+ monitoring, reporting and verification processes?
3. What could be an example implementation of AutoML technology in REDD+?
4. What are views of selected REDD+ and machine learning experts on the use of AutoML technology in REDD+ monitoring, reporting and verification processes?
5. *Does the black-box nature of AutoML technology affect the **reflection** processes of value-sensitive design and responsible innovation software development methods?*

Thesis structure

This thesis is structured as follows. In the first chapter, MRV processes in REDD+ are explained, elaborating on the current technical, social and practical issues found in literature (RQ1). In this chapter, also Machine Learning and AutoML technology are introduced.

In the second chapter, several research methodologies for software development are introduced (RQ2). These methodologies will form the basis of the prototype development, found in the next chapter.

In the third chapter, the prototype application and its functionality is explained (RQ3). Furthermore, the methodology of the research is introduced.

In the fourth chapter, the AutoML prototype tool and its potential use is researched with the help of expert reviews with REDD+ and machine learning (RQ4).

The discussion explores the methodology used, the results found and the ethical questions surrounding the use of AutoML in monitoring. In the conclusion, I will elaborate further on what the results of the research mean for future development, with advice for future software development of AutoML in REDD+ (RQ5).

2.2 The importance of monitoring in REDD+

REDD+ projects are focussed on forest protection, climate mitigation and poverty alleviation. Compared with classical PEFS (Payments for Ecosystem Services) forms of forest protection, REDD+ is a more elaborate program, combining forest protection with carbon sequestration and ecosystem services (GOFC-GOLD, 2012). Monitoring REDD+ is complex, with four tier levels of monitoring quality and methods. Each method is more elaborate, capturing more data and providing a higher quality analysis of the forest area. Higher tier levels of monitoring allow for better information and analyses of carbon capturing, the forest condition and the actual rate of deforestation and land degradation. These sources of information are necessary in REDD+ projects, as the REDD+ financial aspects (such as direct payments) can not function without the necessary data (Angelsen et al. 2018).

Without monitoring, a land owner could claim not to have cut down trees, whereas they actually have been cut down. Therefore, in order for land-owners to keep receiving REDD+ funds, they need to have certain methods of monitoring and reporting of forest changes. Several technical challenges follow this requirement. In 2010, specific REDD+ guidelines of monitoring and reporting were created to standardise MRV processes. (CBB guidelines, Panfil et al. 2016). With the standardisation came several methods of monitoring, reporting and verification. Each of the methods use different forms of software and data-sources to generate data for forest monitors. As in this thesis, the focus is on a new monitoring method based on software and thus computer technology innovation, I have focussed the explanation of the existing monitoring methods on the software technology used.

2.2.1 Software in the REDD+ monitoring processes

In this part I will present an overview of software used in the monitoring processes of REDD+ projects. The overview also focusses on the limitations and strengths with current monitoring methods.

The basic principles of REDD+ monitoring are described in monitoring guidelines, as provided by GOFC-GOLD (2012).

Pixel-Based (Tier 2 level)

In general, for REDD+ projects, deforestation is monitored with “pixel-based” methods. These methods use medium/low-resolution satellite data (30m resolution, Landsat). To calculate forest cover, the amount of green pixels is used to calculate the size of the forest area. If there are 100 green pixels, the forest area is thus around 3000 (100 * 30) square meters (Aragão et al. 2010).

In Figure 2.2, a graphical representation of pixel based data collection is shown. The red pixels in the figure are deforested areas due to forest fire, green pixels are forests where fires took place, but no deforestation took place. The figure indicates primarily the resolution of pixel-based analyses. As the resolution is low, in-depth analyses of data like carbon sequestration, local, small-scale deforestation or forest degradation are not possible with this method (Tokola, 2015). The method is computationally basic, does not require expensive hardware or software and can operate with low resolution input data. It was therefore the preferred method of most REDD+ projects for a long period of time (Sandker, 2021). Advancements in monitoring hardware, such as satellite capturing resolution, have lead to new forms of data analysis, such as the use of multispectral imaging.

Multispectral (Tier 3 level)

A higher resolution form of monitoring in REDD+ is the use of multispectral satellite data. This method uses a wider band of electromagnetic radiation. Whereas the pixel-based method only uses visible light, the multispectral method uses light which is invisible to the human eye. It can therefore

collect data with a much higher resolution and for various purposes, such as soil and vegetation type (Helmer et al. 2015).

The method requires more computational power, and more advanced algorithms than the pixel-based methods. It is therefore more expensive to operate, and thus not as commonly used as the Tier 2 level monitoring method (Bucki et al. 2012).

Although the method collects more data as the previous pixel-based method, the resolution and the data collected can still not be used to detect small-scale forest changes and real-time forest degradation (Bos et al. 2019).

LiDAR with ground-sampling (Tier 4 level)

The most advanced monitoring method in REDD+ is the use of laser-based 3D scanning methods. These methods use LiDAR hardware, which is hardware capable of generating a very highly detailed three dimensional map of the forest. This method requires expensive hardware, is very slow in the creation process and uses advanced 3D modelling software. Due to the cost and requirements, the method has only been used in pilots (Mitchell et al., 2017).

Figure 2.3 - LiDAR scan of forest (WUR, 2014)

With the use of LiDAR, a detailed map can be generated, and thus information about carbon sequestration and total biomass of the forest can be calculated. Due to the slow creation process however, the method is not capable of (near) real-time forest monitoring.

2.2.3 Overview of technical challenges in the REDD+ MRV processes

Many of the challenges in REDD+ MRV processes come forward from limitations in software and data availability. The current implementation of software, and the way MRV processes are set-up, leads to certain challenges, which partly or fully depend on MRV software and hardware.

High-resolution analyses

One of the main issues with REDD+ models for calculating deforestation is the lack of resolution (detailed information), on the forest. The size of the pixels used to analyse forests are big, and do not contain enough information to monitor carbon sequestration, type of vegetation and various other factors which are necessary to monitor forest degradation (Bos et al. 2019). In the paper of Bos et al. (2019), the need for locally calibrated models is explained. The creation of such models would however require high-resolution data. This type of data can not be analysed with a pixel-based model. As a pixel-based model only looks at the colour of a pixel, the variation in pixel colour with a high-resolution image would be too large, and would require additional algorithms specifically calibrated for a region.

Figure 2.2 - Resolution of pixel-based

Community Involvement

Although UN-REDD describes the REDD+ program with the goals of integrating communities in several monitoring activities, in practice, there is limited to no community involvement (Danielsen et al. 2013). Although local community involvement has been shown to be beneficial in the monitoring process, there are multiple difficulties in involving them with the MRV processes.

High costs

2.3 Conclusion on challenges in REDD+ MRV processes

The REDD monitoring, reporting and verification processes have various challenges, related to limitations in software, hardware and social systems in place.

The monitoring and reporting systems in place are highly technical in nature, do not involve local communities or local governments, but instead rely on low-resolution satellite or multispectral imaging, which is unable to detect small-scale real-time changes and generate detailed forest analyses. Monitoring forests for REDD, which ideally requires high levels of detail due to monitoring of the carbon sequestration, is difficult and expensive.

The lack of carbon market integrations also makes the required higher levels of forest monitoring for carbon sequestration largely useless. For the majority of REDD+ projects, no carbon sequestration levels are monitored, whereas in the official UN-REDD guidelines, this is describe as essential for monitoring the involvement of the forests in climate change (Enrici et al. 2018). The lack of financial incentives and the incredibly high monitoring costs involved with higher levels of monitoring cause little to no projects to invest in these monitoring solutions (Ehara et al. 2020). One of the reasons is the required involvement of ground-sampling with traditional monitoring methods, which needs to be performed by locals which are familiar with the forest and it's surroundings/vegetation. As most REDD project officers prefer not to include local communities in their projects, but instead transfer the monitoring power of the forest to large corporations or governments, their involvement is marginalised (Bayrak et al. 2020).

For several of these large problems, new monitoring technologies, with the use of powerful (but inexpensive) computer hardware could help to mitigate some of the monitoring and reporting problems within REDD+. In scientific communities, various platforms, technologies and pilots have been run to integrate new forms of computer technologies in the REDD+ monitoring process (Sandker et al. 2021). However, in the following overview of pilots and studies, most of these technologies are either, not applicable on a large scale, or insufficient as they do not take into account local communities and their problems.

REDD criticism has also been pointed towards the power imbalance between agribusinesses and indigenous people or small-scale farmers. The REDD program has no policies in place to reduce the imbalance which is one of the main causes of deforestation. Although the program is intended to support local communities, researchers note that in most projects, there is little to no local community involvement (Makatta et al. 2015).

Although the program as a whole has been widely successful, with a global reach and effect. Projects under the REDD+ “nomer” are not coordinated from a single organization or nation. Each REDD+ project is unique and tailored to the needs of the community, nation and local area. As the REDD+ program enables transfers of financial funds, data gathering is an essential part of REDD+ projects to verify and monitor the validity and justified transfer of monetary benefits. Unfortunately, gathering detailed data, especially in developing countries, is a challenge. Although satellite data is sufficient for lower tier levels of REDD+ reporting, critics in literature report the lack of ground-sampled data and

higher quality forms of data analysis as one of the main limitations of the potential and reach of REDD+ projects (Duchelle et al. 2015).

2.4 AutoML in forest monitoring

As a new and only recently (in the past ten years) developed technology, Automated Machine Learning data analysis methods are not yet used in the monitoring tools of REDD+. In this part of the chapter, I will explain what AutoML technology encompasses, and how it could fit within the existing tier level system of monitoring methods.

Basics of Machine Learning

In the past decade, the use of Artificial Intelligent software products has accelerated exponentially. The commodification of performant silicon, with advancements in software quality, have made several AI applications commonplace in products used by millions of users worldwide (Adadi et al. 2018). The term “AI” however, is too broad for the applications developed by researchers and developers today. Since 2012, the terms “Machine Learning”, “Big Data” and “Deep Learning” are more commonly used to describe self-learning and semi-intelligent computer technology. The three terms form the basis of most innovations related to data science today, and have revolutionised the way data is researched and used in practice.

Machine Learning and Deep Learning both refer to new methods of analysing data with self-learning technology. The technology can be defined as follows:

“Machine learning is the study of computer algorithms that allow computer programs to automatically improve through experience” (Tom Mitchell, 1997).

The use of Artificial Intelligence in research and product development has accelerated exponentially. Self-learning algorithms are used to process petabytes of data daily (Google Cloud, 2020). With the wide range of possibilities with data analysis, also comes difficulty in explaining the scope and technical standards. Artificial intelligence is a complex technology, and for the coming chapters in this thesis it is therefore important to have a clear understanding on how the technology works, and what the current and future possibilities are. At the moment, AI technology is already being used by millions of people, in simple applications such as categorising photos or recognising your voice. These applications use an AI technique called Machine Learning. Machine learning is the first step towards artificial intelligence. The ultimate goal of artificial intelligence technology is for the workings of AI to be indistinguishable off that of a human brain (Wang, 2006). At the moment, this is still a vision of the future, but a small part of this step is thus already available in the form of machine learning. The machine learning technique is not yet a neural network like the brain but rather focuses on processing large amounts of data with self-learning statistical techniques. The technology differs from standard data analysis (statistical) methods as self-learning, whereas the classical methods are not self-learning and programmed manually (Feurer et al. 2015). Exactly how this works will be explained in this chapter. In addition, the problems within forest monitoring and REDD+ projects are discussed. These problems are partly caused by the limitations of current data analysis methods.

The basics of Machine Learning continued

Machine learning is a method to perform data-analysis. Since the creation of computers, software has been written to analyze data. Usually, data analysis is performed with the use of algorithms. These can be simple in form, like a linear regression, or more advanced, with multiple linear regressions and squared formulas. In statistics, algorithms are created with the use of a fixed set of input and output variables (Feurer et al. 2015)

The statistical analysis of classical methods is performed by clearly defined rules of manipulation and calculation, and the formula's generated by statistical software can be interpreted by the end-user. Machine learning follows a different approach. Instead of "hand-coding" the formula's for statistical analysis, they are generated by a self-learning algorithm (Feurer et al. 2015).

How AutoML works

A machine learning model needs to be trained. In the training process, the model is fed a large amount of data. The data can be of various sorts, it could be images, video, numerical data, text or sound. In essence, all data is formed of numerical data, and thus it can be analyzed with machine learning. In Figure 2.3, the process of machine learning with an AutoML application (CreateML developed by Apple Inc.) is shown. In this case, the model is going to predict which animal is inside the image. The result is the image classifier ML model. In Figure 2.5, the simple output process of the model is shown.

In Figure 2.4, the images are categorized in folders, corresponding to the animal. This the training data added to the AutoML application, shown in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 - Categorization of training data (Apple, 2020)

With machine learning, a part of the data is used to train the model. Usually, 80% of the data is used to generate the mathematical formula's. The remaining 20% of the data is used to improve these formula's with self-learning methods.

After the formula's are generated, the model will compare the output of the model with the training data. If the results do not fit, the model will alter the formula's until they fit the data provided (Hutter et al. 2019). This is a reiterative process, the model will predict and adapt to the data until the model "fits" the data. Depending on the quality of the provided data, the computationally heavy re-training of the model is performed numerous times.

An example of what the content of the image would be with high resolution remote sensing data is provided by Kaggle, a platform for open-source machine learning data. With the data provided by Kaggle, research into machine learning is made possible (Planet, 2017).

In Figure 2.6, example images are given captured by the high resolution PlanetScope satellite system. The images have already been classified with example categories that could be useful for detecting deforestation. The data the model would use is clearly visual data. However, each photo has a

Figure 2.7 - Overview of a classical machine learning model (Uddin et al. 2019).

classification attached to the picture, also called a “string”. There is a possibility of using multiple strings per picture. With more advanced AutoML model builders, each picture could also have additional numerical data.

Based on the classifications given to each picture, the machine learning software will train itself to predict the right classification for each new image analyzed. There are however many steps involved in the process of data collection to a working model.

In Figure 2.7, this process of analyzing visual data is shown with “classical” non-automated machine learning methods. This means, when performed by an expert in machine learning, these are the technological steps taken to form the model. As can be seen from the multitude of steps, the process is convoluted and requires expert knowledge in mathematical and programming areas. The multitude of steps is reduced with AutoML technology. In Figure 2.7, the same process is shown, but now with AutoML technology. In Figure 2.8, it is shown that the entire process of a machine learning model (Figure 2.7) is integrated into the AutoML cloud. The only work necessary is the addition of the dataset, some optimization metrics to fine-tune the model and considerations regarding the amount of computer power needed to build the model. Overall, the amount of steps has been drastically reduced, and the expert knowledge required to build the model is limited.

Even more so, the steps normally performed for a classical machine learning model do not require specialized hardware. Each and every step of Figure 2.7 runs in server parks managed by companies like Google, Amazon or Microsoft. There is no need to install or configure any software. The configuration of machine learning software and packages is one of the more difficult aspects in the model creation process. AutoML does not require specialized software, and thus could potentially be used by a wider range of end-users, that do not have the knowledge or skills to set-up machine learning software (Hutter et al. 2015).

Figure 2.3 - Creation process of AutoML (Apple, 2020).

After the model is created, it can now be used in a wide-range of software applications. These applications could run on mobile devices, on desktop computers or in the cloud. Most companies focus on providing cloud-based solutions, with some exceptions (e.g. Apple). With these cloud applications, the computational power necessary for machine learning is located at a server park. This would enable end-users with limited computer power to operate machine learning without the need for investments in expensive computer hardware (Google Cloud, 2020).

Overall, AutoML is a technology which enables machine learning uses without the need for expert ML programming and mathematical knowledge. The technology only requires a basic understanding of statistics and programming. The cloud-based operation of the technology also enables its use with low computing power.

This part of the chapter was a quick overview of AutoML software. In the next part, I will dive deeper into the challenges related to AutoML technology.

Figure 2.5 - Output of the AutoML model (Apple, 2020)

Challenges associated with AutoML technology

As a new technology, automated machine learning is still in active development. Although continuous improvements are made to the technology, there are certain challenges and potential problems with the technology. AutoML provides technical solutions for some of the inherent problems in machine learning. I will explain some of the problems most common in machine learning and present how AutoML provides a solution.

Figure 2.6 - Categorized high-resolution remote sensing data (Kaggle, 2017)

Bias in model output. Bias might be present due to the way results are gathered. For example, if a model for a certain data-set is developed, the input data for this model might come from areas with a dominant tree species. The model could be trained in such a way that areas with this tree species deliver excellent results. However, due to the lack of data from the areas with other tree species, the model starts delivering wrong results for less common tree species.

Reliability of the model. There are currently no implementations of the technology in the domain of REDD+. Whether the models will deliver reliable results is thus unknown. AutoML however has been used for detecting deforestation in satellite images (Kaggle, 2017), and there are many other use-case of the technology. The reliability of the analyses will depend on the quality of the model. In AutoML, the general consensus is that, the larger and higher quality the data-set, the better the model will perform (Feurer et al. 2015). With larger amounts of (high quality) data, the model will likely perform better, but this is not a given guarantee. Large volumes of data could be collected, with the end result being an unusable model. The software of AutoML applications have built-in indicators for the reliability of predictions given, but can not change the performance of the model, as this is dependent on the quality and type of data.

Quality of the model is thus dependent on the accuracy of the data, such as the classifications. When these classifications are performed by non-experts, there could potentially be some problems with the accuracy. The AutoML software has various indicators which present information about the quality of the data provided. Using AutoML evaluation tools, the software can even detect outliers and alarm strange behavior in the data-set, allowing experts to quickly assess and identify potential quality issues.

Figure 2.8 - The AutoML process (Medium, 2020)

3. AutoML and differences with standard ML (practical considerations)

To explain the creation of a machine learning model, in-depth statistical and mathematical knowledge is required to fully understand and use machine learning algorithms. The need for in-depth knowledge about machine learning is exactly the problem automated machine learning set-out to tackle. Machine learning models could be very useful in all sorts of applications, however, the steep learning curve involved with the creation of these models has prevented developers, researchers and students to have limited interaction with the technology (Feurer et al. 2015).

With the ever increasing computational powers of electronic devices like smartphones, tablets and desktop computers, the use of machine learning has increased ten-fold in the past few years (TechRepublic, 2018). With the large influx of financial investment into the field, companies like Apple and Google set-out to create easier and more innovative forms of the AutoML technology. The goal of Google was to create a set of AutoML tools which would allow regular programmers, such as those working on mobile applications and websites, to work with machine learning. As machine learning is statistical and mathematical in nature, developers have limited experience with machine learning concepts and thus lack the knowledge to implement the technology inside their software applications (Hutter et al. 2019).

2.5 MRV Stakeholders in REDD+ and potential use of AutoML

Stakeholders in REDD+ interact with a monitoring software directly or indirectly. To research the potential uses of AutoML in REDD+, I gathered information about stakeholders in REDD+ and their relation with monitoring software. In the following part, I will introduce the potential ways several stakeholders could use AutoML based monitoring software.

National governments

National governments play a large role in the management of REDD+ programs, such as the set-up of systems to collect and analyze forest data. In the graph (Figure 2.13) below an overview is given for the responsibilities and steps that need to be taken by governments for proper monitoring of REDD+ (USAID, 2014).

The steps in this graph show the decisions that need to be taken in the remote sensing part of the MRV process. As a monitoring tool, the AutoML method would be relevant for a number of these decisions, such as the satellite data sources, options for automation and analysis/results part. National governments can decide if and how AutoML would be used. In order for governments to consider the use of AutoML, the technology will need to be able to replace or add to the existing monitoring tools currently in use. AutoML technology would need to be a positive addition to the program, and adhere to the regulations and conditions set by national and international bodies like the UNFCCC.

Private investors and forest (land) owners

According to the UNFCCC, private investors can be divided into two groups, the first group consists of actors who are involved in the sale of certificates (Verified Emission Reductions, VER's). These are carbon dioxide reduction programs. The second group involved with REDD are the agricultural sector and other drivers of deforestation, such as companies producing timber.

The first group of VER traders have a large interest in the REDD+ program. Certificates are sold for a specific amount of carbon, to governments and private companies. In this group there are also investors in REDD+, these investors invest in order to sell VER certificates. Reliability of data flows for investors is important, especially in the start-up phases of new projects, where carbon estimates need to be calculated (Ehara et al. 2019).

Companies who buy VER certificates do this for a few reasons, in a study by Ehara et al. 2019, companies indicated that these certificates were bought for "image enhancing" reasons related to

carbon reduction. Some firms are also active in the satellite image analysis, aiding research for NGO's and developing countries or are active in planting trees. However, most common reason given was to improve the company's image, as when the company buys VER, it can announce lower carbon emissions and produce marketing material related to preventing deforestation.

The companies involved with VER mention that the MRV process is very costly, and thus efficiency is lacking. The high costs associated with MRV are a common returning theme in scientific literature and also company opinion. As Köhl et al. (2020) discussed, the balance between reduction of CO₂ and conservation efforts is skewed, as most effort needs to be put into the CO₂ part, whereas most companies feel the conservation activities are more important. This indicates that the driver for this group of stakeholders in the MRV process of REDD+ is mostly related to cost. The current monitoring methods in REDD+ are expressed by private companies to be costly, this leads to challenges with the profitability of CO₂, ultimately leading to less private sector interest and thus less private funding in REDD+ (Ehara et al. 2019).

Sub-National governments

A group which could become more important for REDD+ MRV processes in the future are sub-national governments such as provinces and municipalities. A study from Barletti et al. 2018 shows most national governments take full control over the REDD+ projects, where sub-national parts of the government are sometimes included, but mostly excluded from decision making. The authors of the paper mention how including this stakeholder in the REDD+ process could improve upon several factors. Sub-national governments often have better overview of the local needs of their community. They could guide local monitoring efforts more effectively. In the paper, the authors also mention that sub-national governments are the link between local communities and the government. This group of stakeholders could thus play a larger role in the REDD+ MRV process, with potentially new software monitoring methods, this group could receive more agency, depending on the implementation and execution of the monitoring method.

Local Communities

There are a few different forms of local communities in REDD+ programs.

Communities directly involved with REDD+ receive financial support from the program to manage the forest, often have territorial claims on the land, and are responsible for many aspects of the forests condition. This group is quite small but does have a large influence on the forest. They're also the groups most pilot projects used in their use of a software based monitoring tool, as these communities have excellent knowledge about the state of their forest they can perform analyses on the same quality level as experts (Pratiharst et al. 2013). These communities, depend on the data gathered by the monitoring system, as it provides them with financial benefits.

Local community integration in REDD+ is often missing, even though local communities have the knowledge and capacity to manage the forest (Pratiharst et al. 2016).

Other groups are communities who live in the "protected" area, but do not need it for their livelihood or communities indirectly involved with REDD+. The differences between communities could also affect the way monitoring methods are utilised by communities. For example, local communities living inside the protected area might have financial incentives to participate, however, communities not dependent on the forest might not have a financial incentive to participate. According to Danielsen et al. (2013) financial measures should be part of monitoring methods to enhance local community involvement. Because AutoML is not yet researched in REDD+ it is unknown what the exact role of local communities could be with a new monitoring tool and whether local communities would want to cooperate.

Figure 2.13 - Overview of the MRV process in REDD+ (USAID, 2014)

2.6 Potential AutoML use-cases

Based on the capabilities of AutoML technology and the existing application of machine learning in deforestation monitoring, several potential use-cases of monitoring in REDD+ could be possible. The main difference between Automated Machine Learning and “Classical” Machine Learning is the way the software is able to be used by non-experts in artificial intelligence. Existing research into machine learning and forest monitoring can thus indicate several use-cases of automated machine learning.

Reducing forest degradation and providing carbon stock estimations

In the paper of Chen et al. (2018), the authors used machine learning technology to estimate above-ground biomass.

A potential use-case of AutoML technology is the estimation of forest degradation, and changes in carbon stock. Estimating these changes with current monitoring methods requires large amounts of (ground sourced) data. With the AutoML model, forest degradation events would be monitored and reported in real-time with only limited data available. Ground-sampled data, gathered by, for example local communities, could be used to train a machine learning model (Torres, 2014).

The opposite of forest degradation is also possible. The forest can also improve its carbon sequestration ability by for example the growth of total vegetation cover. This is also a possible factor that can be monitored with the use of a machine learning model (GOF-C-GOLD, 2014).

Possible questions related to this use-case are involved with reliability, inclusivity and efficiency concerns. For example, Machine Learning requires a large amount of data, including ground data. Currently, ground (carbon stock) data is gathered by the use of a sample. The size of the sample is often a small area of the total forest being protected. However, Machine Learning requires large sample sizes to be able to predict future changes (Chen et al. 2018).

Determining baselines

In the paper of Grinand et al. 2020, the authors used machine learning to forecast deforestation patterns, similar to current baseline models used in REDD+.

Setting a baseline is an important part in the process of REDD+ monitoring. A baseline is used to determine whether the rate of deforestation has lowered compared to a scenario without REDD+. With the remote sensing and locally sourced data, the model could generate a baseline that acts as a future reference for determining carbon stocks and deforestation. With potential efficiency and thus cost effectiveness gains, more localized baselines could be made. Current baselines are usually nationwide, and thus not precise enough to determine local changes in deforestation. Localized baselines however are too expensive to be made with current methods (Torres, 2014). Based on the capabilities of classical Machine Learning, AutoML could potentially generate localized baselines without the high development costs. With a localized baseline model, the future changes of the forest could be analyzed at a much higher level of resolution.

Determining deforestation with forest inventory

In the paper of Kumar (2016), and the paper of Mayfield et al. (2016) the authors describes how machine learning could be used to determine deforestation.

The process of deforestation is currently monitored with Tier 1 (based on general data) or Tier 2 systems (based on national forest inventories). The systems use low-resolution satellite imagery to determine the extent of deforestation. The analyses made with these systems result in coarse estimations of deforestation. However, although the used remote sensing technologies have a low resolution, large-scale deforestation efforts can be easily picked up, even by these low resolution systems (GOF-C-GOLD, 2014). With machine learning, the analyses of this low-resolution data could be improved by adding locally sourced ground data. By combining the low-resolution remote sensing and the ground data, a high-resolution forest inventory could be made, which could act as a reference for determine future deforestation. The result of using machine learning would thus be an improvement in accuracy or quality of the low-resolution pixel-based method.

Real-time monitoring of forests

With a basic image classification model, changes in remote sensing data can be picked-up and classified. For example, a change in an image from forest cover to forest cover with brown spots could indicate selective logging. The image classification model would classify this change within the image. This is potentially useful for the prevention of small-scale forest degradation drivers. Instead of responsible to forest change every year, the model would allow for near-real-time monitoring. There are multiple applications for this method to be thought of, for example, local communities could receive

notifications of changes in the forest, or national governments could use the method to produce more frequent reports about the forest.

At the moment of writing this thesis, no real-time monitoring deforestation method was developed with the use of machine learning technology.

3. Software development research methods

Introduction

AutoML is not yet used in REDD+, but future implementation could form the basis of new monitoring tools. In order for these tools to be developed, further research for AutoML development is necessary. To research software development, several methods are widely used in computer sciences, human-computer interaction research and innovation. In this chapter, I will discuss some of the most cited and popular approaches which are used to develop and research the creation of software. The goal of this chapter is to analyze and reflect on the software development methods for researching the use of AutoML in REDD+. At the moment of writing, no studies have been published surrounding the topic of AutoML in REDD+. To support the research of this study, the conceptual framework will analyze multiple approaches towards software development. I have gathered four of the most relevant methods discussed in the scientific community today. These methods are widely used in the scientific community and are universally present in the software industry. The methods analyzed are Agile software development, user-centered design, value-sensitive design and responsible innovation.

3.1 Agile software development

One of the latest and most popular methods in the field of software development is called “Agile”. Introduced in 2001, it became increasingly popular to be used for the development of more complex software, such as mobile applications (Brhel et al. 2015). The basis of the method, is flexibility and leanness. In the method, Agile is described as an adaptive development method, meaning its development process will change during time, depending on the progress made with the software, and the experiences from its users.

Adaptiveness and flexibility are core ideas to the Agile approach, and form the basis of multiple variations that have been developed over time. With these variations, there are differences in the approach towards software development. Some of the approaches within Agile development are

targeted more towards the division and organization of tasks between developers, other variations are more general and focus more on the overall development process. One of the most popular, and most general, variation is called “crystal”. The Agile crystal methodology is based on a few key values, such as reflective improvement, osmotic communication, clear focus of direction and easy access for expert users. Most of the variations have approaches focused on common principles, user-interactions, high-quality software, good customer collaboration and responding to change. In general, the most important aspect of the Agile development approach is providing software developed with continuous feedback throughout the development process (Cockburn, 2002).

3.1.1 Discussion

Although Agile has been widely used in scientific research and in practice, there are some limitations to the method which make it less suitable for use in this thesis. In the paper of Lopez-Martinez et al. (2016), the authors found several practical problems with the Agile approach in practice. The first problem could be found in the direction of the framework itself, which is very much focused on the role of programmers and managers, and less so on stakeholders. Although the agile “manifest” describes stakeholder interaction and frequent feedback loops, in practice, the method is suited more for developers and their interactions with each other. Outside stakeholders are rarely considered, and although they are described in the method, their influence and methodology to integrate them with the development is lacking (Lopez-Martinez et al. 2016).

The practical implementation of the principles makes the framework less suitable for a wider socially challenging study such as this thesis. Based on the scientific papers and my own experience in programming, the framework seems to be mostly usable for implementation in the development process of AutoML for the company or organization designing the application or writing the code. Overall, the Agile method seems less suited for the study of this thesis, as Agile approach is technical in its nature and therefore too narrow in its focus on the programming and organizational part. The framework would also not include important aspects related to the moral and ethical questions surrounding the use of AutoML. The demands of end-users in this approach are taken into account in the method, but in practice do not play an important role. Overall, the Agile development approach would be too limited in its scope for the study of this thesis. However, certain elements of the Agile method could still be used for this thesis, such as the integration of stakeholder interaction and feedback loops. The Agile approach could also be useful in the practical development process of the tool within a certain developer group, as an internal tool to improve the development process.

3.2 User-centered design

A second approach towards software development can be found in the form of user-centered design. This approach uses multiple stages to solve problems within the process of software development, and is widely used in the software industry. User-centered design is similar to Agile, and although both methods are often mentioned in scientific literature, user-centered design has been formed into a global ISO standard (Vredenburg et al. 2002).

The approach of user-centered design (UCD) focuses the development of software on the end-user experience. UCD puts the needs and requirements of corporations at a second place, and sets the end-user at the center of software development. The UCD standard is built around principles, that form the basis of the UCD development process. These principles describe the need to understand users, their task and environment, and how to involve end-users throughout the entire development and design process.

Often confused with user-centered design, human-centered design is a similar development method for software. However, there are some key differences which make it less suitable for the study of this thesis. With user-centered design, the demands of the actual end-users are taken into account, instead of a general end-user. This means that the design specifics are more limited towards a certain type of

end-user. This could mean that the design has increased functionality, which would enlarge the difficulty of operation, but allowing better operation for a more expert type of user (Oviat, 2006).

With human-centered design, the design should be able to be used by every kind of end-user. These are usually software designs which have to be used by a large group of people, like a web browser, mail client and navigation software. In comparison, the user-centered development method is applicable for applications such as video editors, image editing and business/research related software such as SPSS or Excel.

The method of UCD consists of four principles. These principles are guidelines for developer, such as incorporating user feedback to define the requirements and design, having early and active involvement of the end-users, a clear understanding of the user and tasks and an overall iterative design process. To support these principles, developers should gather data with several methods, such as focus groups, usability testing, questionnaires and interviews. Another method mentioned is the use of personas, which are fictional characters who would use the software. Personas distinguish end-users based on their demands and other factors like expertise, age and overall skill-set.

3.3.1 Discussion

Many of the aspects related to UCD approach seem to be useful for research into AutoML development, such as the aspects of integrating end-user feedback, the use of focus groups, interviews and questionnaires. Also the creation of persona's is potentially useful when comparing multiple stakeholders and their demands for a monitoring tool. However, there are also several aspects of the method which are likely too limiting for the responsible development of AutoML for REDD+. UCD is a method which seems to be mostly suitable for the development of general new software, such as a smartphone app or website. The method does not integrate ethical or moral dilemmas nor does it discuss potential conflicts between stakeholders or potential problems arising from certain design decisions. The method also seems mostly suited for design in the literal sense, meaning, the placement of buttons and menu's and more arbitrary details of the development. And is thus less suited for the actual design of the underlying technology. However, there are still several aspects of the UCD approach which could be useful for this study, such as the creation of persona's, the integration of interviews and questionnaires and feedback loops.

Taking these observations into account, I will discuss a relatively new approach in the domain of software development, called Value-Sensitive Design (VSD). VSD is a method often mentioned among the likes of user-centered or human-centered design. The method is build around human values, and on the surface seems to be comparable to the UCD and Agile methods, however, the method is quite different in its set-up and overall scope. VSD is a much broader approach towards software development, it encompasses many more aspects of the developmental process and integrates moral and ethical questions. It also deals with stakeholder conflicts and disrupting technologies.

3.4 Value-sensitive design

The VSD approach describes a method for software engineers to take into account values when designing and developing software. In the early days of software and programming, most computer products were designed from a programmer's mind-set. Software was complicated to use, with specific commands and long lists of instructions. This difficulty in software design lead to many potential end-users having issues operating a computer (Lauesen, 2005). After the introduction of human interface design, values like "universal usability" became important in the development of software. The value-sensitive design approach is a method to integrate values like universal usability in the development of software design. Another focus of the VSD approach is the development of novel technologies, such as social networks and self-learning algorithms. These new technologies have the potential to disrupt society if implemented in "unethical" ways (Friedman et al. 2019). Although papers have been written with regard to privacy and ethics in computer science, there was no encompassing approach combining multiple values in computer science.

The value-sensitive design approach has already been used to develop new technologies such as facial recognition software, cookie notifications and speech recognition. The authors of this approach, Friedman et al. (2019), describe seventeen different methods, such as stakeholders analysis, value scenarios, multi-lifespan design and more. I will present and explain the step-based analysis of the VSD method, based on the paper written by Friedman et al. (2019).

1. Determine the most relevant values.

The first step in the VSD approach is conceptualizing and thus determining the values needed for the product development. The process of determining values is usually with the use of stakeholder involvement, such as interactive sessions with possible end-users, software developers and investors. In everyday language, values usually describe economic worth, as something “has a value”. The values used by the VSD approach have a broader meaning, they are used as a notion of what is important for a person. This could be things like clean air, good science or healthy food. Values are not factual, they can differ per person and also the interpretation of a value can differ. Values are thus not empirical, but depend on the interests and desires of a person. Values are thus formed within a cultural basis (Timmermans et al. 2014). Therefore, when values are used to determine guidelines or a development method, the values need to be well defined before they are used. In order to do this, the values needed for the VSD approach need to be “conceptualized”.

2. Distinguishing explicitly supported values from stakeholder values

Before further conceptualizing the values, first, the VSD approach calls for identifying the stakeholders and subgroups within those stakeholders. The power levels can be extrapolated from literature research, guidelines and other materials. The goal of the determined power levels is to create guidelines that are in correspondence with the possibilities (power) that stakeholders have.

Two different groups of stakeholders are involved with the development of new software. One group, direct stakeholders, are those who will interact with the software, such as end-users. The other group of indirect stakeholders does not use the software, but might still experience effects from the use of it. Such as community members whose financial benefits are related to the results of the monitoring software. A direct stakeholder will have interaction with the software. This could for example be persons performing image classification, capturing high resolution remote sensing data or programmers.

The distinction of stakeholders is often connected to the power level they have. For example, a local community member living in a protected forest could be an indirect stakeholder. The member does not use the developed software, but the software does affect the stakeholder’s environment. With the use participatory design, parts of the software can be developed in such a way that indirect stakeholders are considered during the development process, and their lower power level is compensated for.

3. Handling widely divergent and potentially conflicting stakeholder values

There are many power layers within systems, and introducing new technology might lead to power conflicts. With new technology, the introduced possibilities might influence power levels of stakeholders. For example, a farmer might get more insight in its and no longer needs a technical advisor. Values might also differ between stakeholders. For example, one stakeholder might value economical benefits more over environmental gains. The differences in value could lead to conflicts with the introduction of a new technology. Data collection, for example from interviews, is likely necessary to determine how power levels and values between stakeholders differ.

Friedman also describes how to take into account issues of technical, cognitive and physical competency. For example, AutoML is a new computer technology, non-experts not familiar with the concept of classification might make mistakes when classifying and analyzing the data. There are a lot of edge-cases and potential problems when deploying new software that will need to be ironed out.

4. Map benefits and harms onto corresponding values

After gathering data on the relevant values, stakeholders and possible conflicts, the next step in the VSD approach is to combine both the benefits and challenges of the technology to their corresponding values. A method to identify the harms and benefits for stakeholders resulting from the new software is with the use of “personas” (Pruit and Gurdinn, 2003). With the use of personas, each stakeholder is described several characteristics that could identify the harms and benefits it would experience when using the software. The concept of personas was first developed and used by Microsoft engineers in the design of new software such as Windows and Office (Pruit and Gurdinn, 2003). The engineers describe early pitfalls of using the persona technique, such as unrealistic descriptions and failing to capture real world practical information, and give guidelines for future persona development.

Hazards in software are becoming more prevalent with the introduction of more complex software design. Often, new software builds upon the backbone of many software “packages” found on the open-source internet. These packages often include basic functionality such as the ability to upload images to the internet. Although this is not of any concern, the inclusion of many packages, created by many different developers leads to potential problems with aspects of the software, such as its reliability (Feurer et al. 2015).

Another part of the hazard is in the actual use of the software. When a new tool is introduced, it might have unexpected side effects. For example, face detection software which only works with white skin due to a lack of diverse training data, resulting in bias (Nash, 2021). Or societal effects of the software, as users discover new ways to perform certain actions in real-life, for example, the use of a social platform like Facebook to sell products. With a new monitoring tool, there could be potentially new, yet unthought of, hazards. This concept of “hazard” is an integral part of the VSD approach.

After identifying the values, hazards, possible conflicts, stakeholders and their harms and benefits, the value-sensitive design approach uses a practical, step-based approach in transforming these findings into steps for guideline creation.

5. Iteration and integration of conceptual, technical and empirical investigations.

This final part of the method simply states the design process of a new software solution, where the conceptual findings of the first two parts are integrated. The integration of values into the final software design takes part with the use of several feedback methods. Based on the results of the research, values are related to specific software and hardware features. Taking into account all the data gathered, multiple prototypes and development pathways are created. Further stakeholder feedback differentiates between prototypes and pathways. Eventually, a final product is delivered. With this product, continuing feedback processes should iterate and improve the product further.

Discussion

Overall, the value-sensitive design approach seems to be well suited for the study of this thesis. With this approach, I will be able to discover the most relevant values, stakeholders and their interests and responsibilities. However, with just the value-sensitive design approach, there is also an additional area of this studies focus that is yet unexplored. With the introduction of machine learning and data analysis, there are several aspects related to the ethical side of using these technologies. Often used in conjunction with value-sensitive design, a possible approach to analyze these ethical aspects is called “Responsible Innovation”. In most research papers, responsible innovation is seen as an integral part of the VSD approach. However, responsible innovation has quite a broad and encompassing approach towards software development.

3.5 Responsible Innovation

Novel computer technologies often focus on making life easier by automation. In the past few years, all kinds of software innovation has happened in the area of self-learning algorithms. Some of these

innovations have been quite controversial. For instance, face recognition, now widely used in smartphones and public applications like stalls in airports, has been met with widespread public privacy concerns (Chamikara et al. 2020). Machine learning technology is used to build extensive personal profiles by advertising companies like Google and is used to track minority groups in China (New York Times, 2019). The ethical concerns surrounding the technology are widely documented, with researchers categorizing many risks and “hazards” surrounding its use. Although the technology is thus very capable, there is public debate if its use needs to be guarded from malpractice.

Reflecting on ethical and moral issues surrounding technology is difficult. Researchers and scientists working on new technology are often working without established ethical guidelines. In the past years, for technologies like nano-technology, standards and moral conducts have been created. For novel technologies, such as machine learning, these kind of moral conducts are still evolving. This leads to debates in the public sphere and within companies, such as Google, to think about the applications of their technology. An example of this reflexivity in Google was the use of machine learning for drones. Several Google engineers did not want to participate in the use of their machine learning technology for military applications. After debate, the use-case was scrapped and the project was halted (The Guardian, 2018). To ability to have a public debate, and reflect on technology, is essential in discovering potential ethical problems (Stilgoe et al. 2013).

The approach of responsible innovation methodologically describes how to integrate responsible values into new software design (Stilgoe et al. 2013). Using new technologies, like automated machine learning, could also introduce challenges related to the handling and analysis of data (Feurer et al. 2015). Machine learning is often described as a “black box” method, where the algorithm is too complex to be understood (Feurer et al. 2015). A potential problem could be false predictions of the model. There are likely a lot of potential what-if questions surrounding the introduction of novel technology. Two methods to discover these questions are “upstream public engagement” and “constructive technology assessment”. Another method is called “Real-Time technology assessment”, which is most relevant for the case discussed in this thesis. These three methods all take into account the views of multiple stakeholders and future technology development pathways.

Real-time technology assessment

The goal of the paper written by Guston and Sarewitz is to create a closer relationship between scientists and society. The idea of real-time technology assessment (TA) is to integrate social science and policy research with natural science and engineering from the outset. TA would then be an explicit mechanism that is embedded in the technological innovation process. The basis of TA is in the process of decision making. The method is to make incremental decisions, with manageable consequences and possible error-correction which is both politically and practically feasible. The decision making process should be continuously reflexive, relations between co-evolving components of the system should be apparent and responses should be incremental.

Overall the TA method is based on a sophisticated method of trial-and-error. It does not depend on predictability of the results, but rather the ability to make good decisions in complex systems, which are based on synchronous reflection and adjustment. Most important aspect, as mentioned in the paper of Guston and Sarewitz (2002), is effective communication among potential stakeholders, taking into account the stakeholder capabilities, presence and values. For example, the researchers constructed scenarios of the impacts of the nano-technology, and published multiple scenarios for public feedback. The most relevant aspect of the TA method is the creation of a research set-up that does not presume perfect planning or having foreseen all impacts of the new technology. Instead, with TA, the presumption is that unexpected events will take place, and there have to be pathways in place to deal with these unexpected events. A method to create these pathways is called “midstream modulation”.

The paper from Fisher et al. (2006) discusses reflexive participation, and the ability of scientific researchers to “modulate” the goals and methods of their research during the research process. The authors describe three different approaches to engage participation, upstream, midstream and downstream approaches.

Upstream, midstream and downstream approaches

With an upstream approach, the public is engaged in the scientific debate. The idea is that potential issues with the technology, and the public perception of this technology, can be remedied during the development process. After the technology is introduced, new issues might pop-up from public spheres. The goal is to clearly communicate between stakeholders, find the issues and propose solutions. With a midstream approach, both the public and the scientists work together to determine the goal of new research.

Modulating processes is a different less destructive way of changing technology. Instead of making large changes to a technology, midstream modulation alters the existing activists in accordance with the societal dynamics, which are formed from public debate. An example of this process could be found in the way nano-technology was researched by the Center for Nanotechnology at Arizona State University (Fisher et al. 2006). The midstream modulation approach taken divided the development (research) process into small iterative steps. For each step, the researchers developed multiple innovation paths. Each path was slightly different in its approach, with the main differentiator the “risk” involved with that innovation path. Based on feedback from various stakeholders, both at the University and public, the “best” innovation paths were chosen. Overall, midstream modulation is about taking into account policy, techno scientific and societal factors in the development process of new technology, creating research pathways that differ in their approach. These pathways are then chosen based on feedback and collaboration with various stakeholders.

New issues could pop up after the technology has been introduced and is in use. The ability to recognize new problems with the technology is an essential aspect to mitigate potential ethical and moral problems. This is part of the “responsiveness” concept in the RI approach. In the paper of Fisher et al. (2006), the authors describe several criteria which are important in creating a responsive developing process. These so-called “stage-gate” criteria are guidelines for the development process.

Stage-gate criteria method in responsible innovation

As derived from Fisher et al. 2006.

1. Risks identified, manageable and deemed acceptable

The risks associated with the technology implementation are identified, manageable and deemed acceptable. The first challenge is to identify the actual risks. Identifying risks could be done using literature research or expert interviews.

2. Clear communication

A large challenge when introducing new technology is the creation of documentation. Without proper documentation, mistakes could be made and wrong analyses could be performed. It is the responsibility of the producer of the tool to produce the right documentation.

3. Applications and impacts described and mechanisms put in place to review these

After implementing the technology, there should be certain mechanisms in place to review the impact of the technology. For example, by taking into account the results from the persona stakeholder analysis and determined hazards.

4. Mechanisms identified to understand public and stakeholder views

This last stage is important to identify the ethical considerations of stakeholders. In the value-sensitive design approach, this is already an important part of the method. Stilgoe et al. (2013) describe a

combination of stakeholder mapping exercises and interviews to get an overview of different stakeholder views. These views give an indication into the ethical considerations of stakeholders. For example, maybe public views on the use of machine learning are negative because of mis-use of data, this public view will then need to be identified and can be used to improve the tool or technology.

Overall, the responsible innovation approach provides an elaborate method for the analysis of ethical and moral questions in novel technology. With the use of methods like real-time technology assessments, determining the “stream” approaches and the use of stage-gate like criteria, the responsible innovation approach seems to be well-suited for further research in this study.

Conclusion

AutoML is a novel technology that requires in-depth analyses and proper guidance for future development. The requirements for this thesis’ topic are however broader than most software development research methods offer. For the approaches of Agile software development and user-centric design, the methods could be used in the actual development process of AutoML, however, for describing the guidelines, these approaches are too limited. The focus of the Agile and user-centered approach is prominently on the programming process. The methods describe how the programming process could be optimized to develop an app with lower costs while continuously adapting to end-user feedback. The methods of agile, scrum and user-centered design thus describe in detail how developers could organize teams and optimize their programming work. Although some elements of these approaches could be used for the research of this thesis, the focus of these approaches seems to be mostly limited towards programming practices, and are thus not of great interest for the research of this thesis.

In conclusion, the approach and method of Agile development is unlikely to benefit the study of this thesis. However, some aspects of Agile development, such as lean and flexible development, could be taken into consideration. For the user-centered design approach, some aspects of this approach seem to be useful for this study, such as the creation of personas and the iterative design process, which has feedback loops for every step within the developmental stage.

The approaches of value-sensitive design and responsible innovation seem to be most well-suited for the study of this thesis. AutoML is a socio-technical innovation, requiring the participation of actors from multiple layers in the system, like governments, local communities and NGO’s. These actors have different demands for the software, different expectations and also different levels of expertise with the use of software packages. In the introductory chapters, I discussed several values like reliability, effectiveness and inclusiveness. These values are related to REDD+ program in several ways. They relate to the problems within the program, but also to the expectations of the program. In REDD+ guideline documents written by the UNFCCC, NGO’s and research institutes, values are commonly used to describe the goals within the program. Values are mentioned in documentation and guidelines and form the basis of the programs goals and are related to distinct characteristics of REDD+ programs, such as the monitoring and verification programs (GOFCC-GOLD, 2014). The value-sensitive design approach thus seems to be most well-suited for this study.

Guiding the development of novel software technology has been the main goal of methods like value-sensitive design and responsible innovation. The approaches of user-centered design, value-based design and responsible innovation have concepts and methods that suit the development of AutoML in REDD+. The value-sensitive design approach could be used to determine the most relevant values and stakeholders, their potential benefits and the right guidelines to make sure harms and hazards are reduced. As AutoML is a new technology, with still evolving ethical and moral questions, an additional approach was analyzed called “responsible innovation”. This approach is often used in conjunction with value-sensitive design. After analyzing the approach, many of the concepts and steps seem to be well fitting for researching the development of AutoML. Some of the ideas, such as using multiple development pathways, could be implemented in the research of different use-cases of the method.

For the upcoming expert interviews, the values will play an important role. Based on the feedback from many experts, the most relevant values, stakeholders, potential hazards and benefits will have to be determined. The results from the conceptual framework show the necessity for in-depth analyses in multiple REDD+ domains, as many aspects of the system will need to be analyzed and mapped out.

Overall, value-sensitive design and responsible innovation were found to have relevant concepts and methods for guiding the development of AutoML in REDD+. Both the approaches also seem to be well suited for the development of future use-cases for AutoML technology. The analysis of this conceptual framework also shows the need for further data collection, be it in the form of literature review or interviews. This data collection will need to aid in the formation and development of several of the steps mentioned in the VSD and RI approaches, such as the determination of the important values, stakeholder demands and challenges.

4. Research Methodology

In this chapter, the research methods are elaborated upon, the type of data gathered and how this data was used for the analysis.

In the software development methods chapter, several methods were discussed which describe step-based approaches towards software research and development. These steps include processes like stakeholder feedback sessions, iterative design processes and the creation of development pathways.

In the value-sensitive design method, values form the basis of a software development trajectory. The first step in this method is to determine the values and gather valuable feedback from relevant stakeholders.

To follow the approach of the VSD method, relevant stakeholders will be consulted in the form of interviews. With the interview format, detailed questions can be asked and real-time, interactive feedback upon the values and the prototype app (to be introduced in this chapter) can be provided.

To follow the software development research method, a prototype was developed which show-cases the AutoML technology for a variety of use-cases.

4.1 Development of prototype AutoML demonstration tool

The goal of the prototype app is to give experts insight into the possibilities of AutoML and its functionality related to REDD+ data analysis processes. The experts will be presented with the app's interface, which is a visual representation of the classification process needed to create a functional AutoML model.

The app is developed for a general use-case of AutoML, which is visual object detection, the most common use of machine learning in applications. The development of the prototype application took place in Apple Xcode, a developer program for Apple computing hardware. Xcode contains a visual editor for software interfaces. With the use of the editor, a wireframe application was developed, this means that, only the visual shell of the application is functional. No data is processed or code executed.

In three flowcharts (Figure 4.2), three processes of app operation are depicted. The first process, shown in is called “classification”. In this process, raw data collected is enhanced with additional information. The additional information describes the raw data. Without the description (classification), the machine learning model would not understand what the raw data indicates. Based on the classifications given to the raw data, newly added raw data can be analysed based on the previous classifications.

In the second graph, the classification data is used to generate an AutoML model.

In the third figure, newly acquired data is shown to be analysed with the AutoML model.

With the prototype application, the machine learning classification process is performed with a mobile application. Visual data (from satellite or drone sources) is classified according to certain variables common in current REDD+ data analysis processes, such as types of vegetation and land-use changes.

In the second step, the visual data with the embedded classifications is analysed by the AutoML application. The application connect the raw data to classifications given. With self-learning methods, the goal of the application is to predict the previously provided classifications purely with the raw data without the classifications. The application thus predicts the classification based on a satellite image on the basis of previously provided data.

The third step in the process is to feed the generated model newly acquired data. The goal of the model is now to predict the right classifications to the new data. This means that the ML-model needs to predict a certain variable based on the visual data provided. An overview of all the steps is provided in Figure 4.2.

The prototype was developed to take into account several challenges with REDD+ MRV processes as commonly found in scientific literature, such as the effective use of high-resolution data, the ability to generate localised models that take into account vegetation, local community interaction as well as the ability to calculate carbon sequestration potential. To verify these possibilities and their usefulness in the REDD+ MRV process, I requested feedback on this prototype from various experts with the help of interviews.

4.1 Interviews

4.1.1 Goal and use of prototype in the interviews

The main goal of the interviews is to gather a better understanding on the problems with REDD+ monitoring, reporting and verification processes and how they relate to the possibilities of the prototype application. The interviews will be a supportive part of the thesis, the idea is that they help to identify the most important values and use-cases of the technology with the help of a prototype

application. The interviews are thus meant to give better insight in the practical aspects of using AutoML in REDD+ MRV processes.

To visualize this use-case with an AutoML integration, for use in the interviews, I developed a presentation for the prototype application, which shows how the AutoML technology could work in a REDD+ setting. The prototype in the presentation shows a preliminary user interface which could be used by local communities to classify drone or satellite remote sensing footage. The user interface is a so-called wire-frame, which means that the functionality is envisioned, but does not yet generate any working results.

In Figure 4.1, a screenshot of the prototype is depicted. Inside the mobile app there is a selected area (classification area) and for this selected area, the end-user will need to select several classifiers, such as tree height, density and their confidence in the analysis they are performing. The main purpose of the developed tool is to gather more insight into the practical implications of AutoML technology. As some experts might not be familiar with AutoML, the tool would provide them with an impression of the technology.

Overall, the goal of the prototype in the interviews is to answer the question as to how a technological solution based on AutoML technology could be developed.

4.2 Set-up of the interviews

In order to find experts to interview, I contacted REDD+ experts at Wageningen University and send emails to experts who have published papers in specific areas of machine learning and or REDD+. In total, around 20 emails and invitations for an interview were send. Based on information in some papers, such as details about the use of unmanned aerial vehicle's in a pilot project related to REDD+, I would contact the person or company behind the operation, and plan a date for a face-to-face semi-structured interview.

There are five main versions of interviews. Each interview starts with a short presentation about the possibilities of AutoML in REDD+. This presentation includes the usual introduction of the technology, and some of the challenges and benefits. For data science experts, I included some more information about the technology, such as changes in tier levels, required resolution and processing techniques. The presentation also introduced the prototype, it's functionality and the possible use-cases I envisioned. The time indicated for the presentation and overall introduction was ten minutes. For the entire interview a time of around 45 minutes was planned. The interviews were conducted using web conferencing software, such as Microsoft Teams/ Skype and the audio was recorded with the experts permission.

The interviews were semi-structured, with a fixed set of topics, but with room for me to differ the topic questions depending on the answers of the interviewee.

4.2.1 Interview groups

Figure 4.1 - Wireframe prototype

For each group of experts, were created. The structured with a set of for improvisation but in that would be followed, of the prototype tool, the values and their reflection possibilities of AutoML in were discussed beforehand

different questions interviews were semi-questions, with room general a main theme which is the analysis discussion of the upon limitations and REDD+. Questions with the thesis

Figure 4.2 - Overview of processes of the prototype application

supervisor.

REDD+ expert (social sciences)

The interview is structured to discuss the needs and possibilities of local communities in REDD+, and also included more technical questions surrounding the organization and management of REDD+ MRV methods.

Main goals of the interview are to get information about the challenges resulting from local community involvement. Receive feedback on the values and their integration into the too and reflect upon practical issues and challenges related to the prototype tool.

REDD+ expert (data sciences)

This interview is adapted from the social science expert interview to include more technical information related to tier levels, resolution required for monitoring and other technical REDD+ details. The main goals of this interview are to get technical and practical information regarding the technological aspects of the prototype tool, receive recommendations for future development and reflect upon multiple values like reliability, effectiveness and their relevance within REDD+ MRV processes.

Company working on community driven REDD+ monitoring

There are multiple companies producing products related to community monitoring. The interview questions developed are meant for companies like Cybertracker or CLASlite, working with community monitoring products. The companies produce equipment like drones or portable devices which aid in REDD+ monitoring. The main goals of these interviews is to receive feedback on practical aspects of monitoring and collecting data, and reflect upon the interaction between values, monitoring tools in comparison with the presented prototype tool.

The goal of this interview is to get a better understanding of the technical challenges related to multi-input object detection models. For this interview, the presentation of the prototype tool is adapted with more technical information and also provides more background information regarding REDD+. The main goals of this interview are to gather feedback on general challenges with machine learning software like AutoML, reflect upon the prototype tool, discover what is missing or problematic with the technology and discuss the relevance of certain values and their importance within machine learning applications.

4.3 Interview data analysis

The interviews were transcribed with Apple speech transcription software and manually corrected. The transcribed interviews were thematically categorized and converted into basic mind-maps (Appendix 4.1). With the use of these mind-maps, connections between comments within the interviews were formed. The formulation of mind-maps for interview coding was based on the paper by Wheeldon (2009). Multiple mind-maps were made for different themes, which also form the structure of the upcoming chapter. Special attention in the mind-maps was given to argumentative comments. In the interviews, ethical questions and dilemma's will be presented to the interviewees. Argumentative responses were colour-coded, as negative, positive or neutral towards specific questions. These responses were compared with each other.

4.4 Systematic Literature Review

In addition to interviews, information was gathered from existing monitoring solutions and their accompanying scientific literature, white-papers and guidance documents. The method used for collecting data in this way is called "systematic literature review". As the name suggests, data from scientific sources is collected in a systematic way. By combining multiple sources, information can be collected in a way that a single study can't (Snyder, 2019).

Scientific sources have been found with the use of Scinapse.io, an innovative search engine for scientific literature. Literature has been searched with the keywords "REDD+", "AutoML", "Machine Learning", "monitoring" and other relevant keywords as discussed in this thesis. Keywords were combined with each other to find relevant information for the second and third chapter of this thesis, such as the methods of machine learning used for forest monitoring.

The software development methods of the third chapter were also researched with the help of a systematic literature review. The software development methods were found with similar search terms, such as "software development method", "software design" and "machine learning development".

With the use of the built-in relevant paper finder functionality in Scinapse, I was able to find relevant papers and resources. The search engine also shows the quality of the journal it is published in, and uses machine learning to recommend which papers are most relevant.

4.5 Potential validity of prototype and interviews

One method considered to verify the AutoML technology for REDD+ was to make a fully functional prototype application, which then would produce results which could be compared to other existing monitoring tools. The demands for this kind of analysis would however be very demanding.

For the interviews, the statements made by experts were compared with information collected from various REDD+ and machine learning white-papers, as well as REDD+ monitoring guidelines, such as GOF-C-GOLD (2012).

4.6 Conclusion

With the use of semi-structured expert interviews, data was gathered about the prototype application and potential future development for specific use-cases. In the interviews, questions were formulated to receive feedback on the limitations and possibilities of AutoML technology in REDD+. Furthermore, questions were formulated to gather general feedback on REDD+, including reflections upon values as part of the steps described in the value-sensitive design framework. By also including interviews with machine learning experts, technical details of machine learning development and reflections upon the prototype tool were gathered. With this data, questions surrounding the (technical) abilities of AutoML and the prototype developed could be answered, as well as the usefulness of value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods for the analyses of a black-box technology like AutoML. The gathered data would also aid in the development of future use-cases for the prototype and the AutoML technology in general. This direction of future developed would be based on the experts reflections on the prototype tool and general challenges in REDD+ MRV processes.

For the second and third chapter of the thesis, a systematic literature review method was used to find and assess information related to machine learning, REDD+ MRV processes and software development methods.

5. Expert feedback on AutoML prototype and use-cases

To reflect on and further develop the use-case and development path for AutoML technology, I interviewed experts in various fields working with REDD+, machine learning and computer sciences.

With the use of interviews, experts were able to reflect on issues surrounding the prototype and the overall technology in great detail. The interviews also allowed me to interactively reflect on the arguments presented by the experts. With such interaction, more detailed definitions and findings could be found than with an unstructured or completely structured interview. The structure of the interviews allowed for improvisation and thus additional questions, but at the same time provided a basis which covered all the questions which were important for the development of a use-case of AutoML technology in REDD+.

The prototype presented, which describes a high-resolution remote sensing monitoring system, was developed taking into account the possibilities with current machine learning technology. In scientific literature, challenges with current monitoring method were identified, and the development of the AutoML prototype was adapted towards “solving” those challenges. In the interviews, I discussed this use-case and the technological and social challenges related to the use of AutoML.

5.1 Analysis with the AutoML prototype

The original use-case of the technology was developed to improve upon several shortcomings with current REDD+ monitoring. With the use of a prototype application, the use-case was introduced and explained to the experts. The prototype application introduces several elements of end-user interaction and proposes a way to analyze, and use, AutoML software in REDD+.

The AutoML technology was presented to the experts as an alternative to current monitoring tools and software. In the example use-case of AutoML technology presented, high resolution remote sensing data, from satellites or unmanned aerial vehicle's, would be combined with on-the-ground sampled data. These samples would contain data like tree thickness, density, soil types and other variables. By combining multiple data flows, the goal of the model would be to predict carbon sequestration changes in the forest, and calculate these levels solely based on high-resolution remote sensing data. The

resulting monitoring solution would perform at a Tier 3 level, which is a step-up from most countries Tier 2 level systems.

To investigate the technical possibilities and background of an AutoML monitoring system, I interviewed an expert in REDD+ monitoring, and an expert in machine learning. I asked the experts whether the prototype is technically viable in several ways, such as the collection of data, the analysis and processing of data and the practical use of the model.

The research in this chapter has been structured in the same process as a standard AutoML development process, meaning, first, the method of data collection, then the analysis of this data and ultimately, the model creation and use-case.

Method of data collection

The first step of any model creation is data collection. For the use of the prototype wireframe app, data collection would have to be performed by satellites or unmanned aerial vehicle's (UAV's). A second, more generally used method is the use of remote sensing satellite data. With both these two methods, visual data of the forest is captured. A higher resolution data source generally leads to better results when in use with machine learning (Feurer et al., 2015). UAV's are able to capture much higher resolution imagery than remote sensing satellites (Paneque-Gálvez et al., 2018). In theory, with UAV's, the AutoML technology would thus perform better. However, according to an expert on UAV's, data collection with UAV's would be time consuming and difficult due to multiple reasons, such as the lack of autonomous software for the UAV's (Interview [Expert 7, 09-06-2020]). This would mean the vehicles have to be flown by trained people. Frequent capturing of the forest would also be difficult, as there are very large data flows to be processed. Overall, the expert concluded the use of UAV's would present too many challenges. This was confirmed by a professional UAV flyer, who mentioned that UAV's should be reserved for small-scale projects and would be too time consuming to fly frequently over large areas (Interview [Expert 7, 09-06-2020]).

Reflecting on the technical expert feedback, the UAV data collection option would be unsuitable for use within the AutoML prototype. Although the technology showed promise in REDD+ pilot projects, these projects did not consider the frequent and large area capturing. However, for the practical implementation of REDD+ monitoring, the lack of very high resolution UAV data is not necessarily a problem. With new satellite technology from companies like "[planet.com](https://www.planet.com/)", high-resolution satellite data has been made available on a daily basis. The resolution of their satellite imagery is high (3.7meters/pixel). Related to these new high-resolution data sources, a machine learning expert indicated that the use of this high resolution satellite data is likely sufficient for the purpose of AutoML, which is to indicate general changes land-use (Interview [Expert 2, 07-05-2020]). The [planet.com](https://www.planet.com/) company has also published multiple white-papers and public data-sets for further research into the use of high resolution satellite imagery for machine learning. The results from their white-papers show promising results in this field.

With the use of the prototype application (and further provided background information), experts were able to comment and discuss on the first step of AutoML development, data collection. The next step in the AutoML process is the processing of this data.

Data processing

There are multiple AutoML data processing methods, such as image classification or object detection. Experts in machine learning and data analysis were asked to provide feedback on the prototype application with regards to these two methods. The results of this part show how experts will be able to comment and provide feedback on future AutoML development questions.

With object detection, specific objects can be classified inside a satellite image. In comparison, with standard image classification, the satellite image as a whole is classified. This latter method is thus less precise and does not lend itself towards producing detailed monitoring reports. In the interview with a

machine learning expert, the expert considered object detection however as time consuming for a “proof of concept”. The expert explained that object detection requires a large increase in training and data processing, and that the data should also be high-resolution in order to detect the objects. He also mentioned that, in current research, with the high resolution remote sensing data, object detection is not used as well (Interview [Expert 2, 07-05-2020]).

The second, more widely used option in machine learning, called image classification, was met with positive criticism from the machine learning expert. This is the method also used in current scientific research with the high resolution remote sensing data. Already, there have been AutoML models created with the PlanetScope data for deforestation purposes by multiple machine learning researchers (Kaggle, 2018). However, with image classification, the abilities of the prototype would be more limited than with object detection.

To discover what would be a potential use-case of the technology without object detection would be, feedback from experts was taken into consideration. An expert mentioned that local communities depend on monthly reports from the sub-national government to monitor their territories. These reports are made with low-resolution satellite data and provide limited insight into the changes of the forest. Therefore, he suggested that, based on the information I provided him with, the technology could be used to monitor forest in (near) real-time (Interview [Expert 3, 21-06-2020]).

Reflecting on the findings of the expert and the current scientific research into machine learning, I concluded that deciding upon a data processing method in AutoML requires further research and expert feedback.

Practical implementation

The following part is described as a practical consideration of what is realistically possible with the technology and would also build upon the practical needs in REDD+ monitoring, such as providing real-time analyses of the forest. The information required for the practical implementation is determined by expert feedback, as required in the value-sensitive and responsible software development methods.

As background information for REDD+ experts, I developed a technical introduction into a practical use-case of the AutoML technology with the prototype and additional, technical information about data sources. The data used by the AutoML model in this introduction is high-resolution PlanetScope data. This data is split into plots, and each plot is given a fixed (GPS) location, which allows for location-comparison with new data collected.

An example of the practical use-case of AutoML technology is shown in Figure 5.1, the plot in a specific location could like this on one day, showing no signs of deforestation, but a week later have indications of changes in the forest.

Figure 5.1 - Change in image classification (Kaggle, 2017)

The AutoML model would indicate that, for this specific location, the image classification has changed to primary and selective logging. This indicator could then be used for various analyses, such as

notifying local communities, general forest monitoring or be used by civil society in projects to report on deforestation.

REDD+ experts were asked whether the AutoML technology, in the form of the prototype would be a useful addition to current REDD+ monitoring. Researched aspects were related to the possibility of involving communities, whose role in REDD+ has been debated in scientific literature.

Community driven monitoring

According to an interviewed REDD+ expert, there is a lack of community involvement in REDD+. Local communities are formed by citizens who are involved indirectly or directly with REDD+, for example, communities that live on the land or interact with it. According to this expert, communities lack the tools to discover and proof cases of deforestation on their land. In South-East Asia, she mentioned there is no such thing as a community driven project (Interview [Expert 4, 11-07-2020]). Monitoring is performed by national agencies and private project organisers. Regarding the use-case of real-time monitoring, such use of a monitoring tool could potentially be useful for project monitoring. However, the expert mentioned that local communities in South-East Asia have likely no use for the prototype tool presented, as they are, at the moment, not included in the REDD+ projects. As an alternative, the expert mentioned that the most likely use of a tool would be within civil society projects. These are projects of concerned citizens all over the world who try to draw attention towards deforestation. The REDD+ expert mentioned these projects put pressure on governments to perform better with REDD+. And a real-time monitoring tool such as the prototype could “strengthen their arguments” (Interview [Expert 4, 11-07-2020]).

Another REDD+ expert, who works in Colombia with local communities, mentioned that the REDD+ monitoring of forests, which is performed once per month in Columbia, is challenging. There is only a limited budget available, and the amount of data which needs to be analyzed amounts to large surface areas. As a result, in the “dry” season, when there are lots of fires, the professional monitoring group is unable to tackle small-scale changes in the forest, and can only focus on bigger changes (Interview [Expert 3, 10-06-2020]). According to the expert, a method to detect smaller change would thus be helpful. Local communities in Columbia exist of indigenous people. One of their goals is to protect and validate their territory. The expert mentioned that these community owned areas are large and often difficult to monitor. Local communities also contain mobile devices which they could use to indicate any changes happening in the forest, however, finding these changes is difficult due to the large size of their territory.

Technical monitoring considerations

A REDD+ expert involved with monitoring mentioned difficulties to detect small-scale changes in the forest caused by low-resolution monitoring solutions. These small-scale drivers over time result in forest degradation (preventing forest degradation is one of the goals in REDD+ projects). Current, pixel-based, monitoring tools do not have the ability to detect small changes in the forest (see Figure 5.2 for an example of small-scale changes). An expert in REDD+ mentioned that the new monitoring tool could be a useful addition to the collection of tools if it would provide insight into these small-scale forest degradation events (Interview [Expert 3, 10-06-2020]). According to this expert, the real-time aspect of the prototype tool was not the most important factor, more important is the “ability to undertake practical action to stop small-scale changes”.

A REDD+ policy expert commented that local communities operate at a smaller scale and only play a minor role in the REDD+ monitoring system. A real-time monitoring system would be useful in the monitoring process. As for the question whether local communities are missing a tool, the expert mentioned that the term local communities is too loose and undefined and there is no single project or set-up in REDD+, every country and project is different (Interview [Expert 5, 26-06-2020]). Therefore, according to the expert, what’s missing in the current REDD+ projects would really depend on the goals of the project. For example, for some local communities a very active and precise real-time monitoring tool would maybe not be accepted as some local communities have strong financial benefit

Figure 5.2 - Small scale selective logging in the Amazon rainforest, captured by PlanetScope (planet.com, 2018)

from the forest and deforestation activities (Interview [Expert 5, 26-06-2020]). In some cases, the local communities actually oppose the deforestation projects due to their financial benefits generated from deforestation activities, such as increased agricultural abilities. It's therefore not a given that local communities want to cooperate or would benefit from a new monitoring tool (Interview [Expert 5, 26-06-2020]).

Overall, the expert interviews show that a wide range of applications and possibilities is possible for the AutoML prototype. The experts indicated multiple challenges related to the prototype shown and have delivered feedback on the possibility of using AutoML for the real-time monitoring of forests.

A pilot by Pratihast et al. (2016) showed that, with presumably inferior resolution and detection technology, the real-time monitoring tool would work corresponding to the general requirements of REDD+ projects. Based on the results of this study, the likeliness of real-time monitoring as a viable use-case for AutoML technology in REDD+ was further validated, and the feedback from experts was in line with relevant considerations already discovered in previous scientific studies.

Based on the feedback from experts, I have identified that potential uses of real-time monitoring could be for local communities as a means to protect their territory, as a civil society research tool or as a tool for (sub)-national governments to provide frequent forest change reports. To further assess the possibilities of the tool with regards to value-sensitive design and responsible innovation development methods, I have analyzed the tool further with the methods as discussed in the conceptual framework.

5.2 Risk and benefits of the developed AutoML tool

During the interviews I introduced the goal of the thesis, which is to research a value-sensitive development process for the use of AutoML in REDD+. An important aspect of the value-sensitive development process is the use of values in interviews and other development aspects. To research whether this approach would deliver valuable results, I asked the experts about values like reliability, efficiency, effectiveness and transparency in relation to the presented prototype AutoML tool. For these values, the experts commented on how the presented prototype AutoML monitoring tool would be able to help realize these values in practice. I also asked questions as to how some of these values can be built into the future design of the prototype tool.

Responsible use of AutoML

Responsible use of machine learning is an important topic among scientific researchers. There have been numerous papers published which indicate issues with bias and problems with machine learning in

general. When asked about these problems, experts agree that, with remote sensing data, there are likely less issues with problematic interpretations of the data. However, with every machine learning implementation, there are potential problems, ranging from general unreliability to unforeseen outliers. One of the major concerns of a machine learning expert is the lack of oversight over the “inner” workings of the model (Correspondence [Expert 6, 13-07-2020]). With AutoML, the formulas and code generated is often described as a “blackbox” model. Contrary to common belief, classical machine learning models, as created by the machine learning expert, are hand-written and coded with mathematical formulas. The use of hand-coding the model allows for easier peer-review and verification. With AutoML, not only is the code proprietary for the company providing the service, like Google, but the actual underpinnings of the model are not available as well. The expert [6] mentions that the model created is thus not transparent in its inner-workings.

To prevent problems with the AutoML model, another machine learning expert commented therefore to keep the model as basic as possible (Interview [Expert 2, 09-06-2020]). By taking away “complex data connections” the model would become more reliable, and its use would be easier to implement and control. To guarantee the responsible use of AutoML software, and not have the complex data connections, the machine learning expert suggest to start with a simplified model. A simplified model would provide limited information, however, due to the limited information provided, the model is also easier to verify and is not able to produce wildly inaccurate results (Interview [Expert 2, 09-06-2020]). Further improvement in reliability could be achieved by “comparing the model with existing AutoML solutions”. These solutions exist in the form of research published with PlanetScope forest data on platforms like GitHub (Kaggle, 2018).

To discover issues with responsible use, the implementation could first be tested on a smaller scale. An expert commented to use the technology first in pilot projects. The same statement was given by another expert in REDD+ monitoring. For these pilot projects, the use of a basic real-time monitoring could already be useful (Interview [Expert 3, 10-06-2020]). An expert who is also active in the public domain, related to the promotion of REDD+ projects, mentioned that civil society could use this technology to report and investigate deforestation, before the technology is more widely used in bigger projects. According to machine learning experts, Issues with responsible use in a real-time monitoring model are less likely to pop-up, as the image classification method is more limited in it’s technological scope (Interview [Expert 2, 09-06-2020]). Based on expert assessment, the responsible use of AutoML could be realized with the use of initial pilot projects. These pilot projects would then be used to determine further developmental steps and discover potential shortcomings of the tool.

Reliability of monitoring

An expert in REDD+ monitoring mentioned that, if the AutoML tool is not reliable, the models’ usability in the monitoring system would be limited (Interview [Expert 1, 07-06-2020]). Unreliability would be a reason for this expert not to use the technology. For machine learning experts, the use of automated machine learning also exposes bigger challenges with reliability. For these experts, reliability means having no strange outliers and potential false outcomes of the model (Interview [Expert 2, 09-06-2020]). A machine learning expert mentioned that the AutoML tool should be limited to a simplistic goal of providing simple image classification labels until more data is available about its reliability (Interview [Expert 2, 09-06-2020]). The machine learning expert also concluded that, in the beginning stage of the models development, the model should only predict change or no change, in the plot, like a one or a zero. After proving this would work the model could be extended further (Interview [Expert 2, 09-06-2020]).

Effectiveness and efficiency of the tool

Effectiveness for machine learning experts is related to the use-case of the technology. According to one machine learning expert, an effective model is able to achieve real world results, which would mean alerting local communities of changes in the forest and assisting national forest institutions in their search for forest degradation drivers (Interview [Expert 3, 10-06-2020]). Another machine learning expert, also mentioned that the potential effectivity should be researched before the data collection of

the model begins (Correspondence [Expert 6, 13-07-2020]). Data collection and model building is time consuming and requires funding for the computing power. According to the experts, effectiveness of an AutoML model is enabled by simplicity. In scientific literature, the operation of AutoML model is mentioned in the need for computing power, and a simple, but effective model is not only cost saving, but also efficient to operate, update and run (Feurer et al. 2015).

For social REDD+ experts, effectivity depends on the practical results the tool would deliver. The expert mention that tool should be able to monitor without the need for large investments (Interview [Expert 1 & 4, 2020]). One expert mentioned that the tool should not require continuous funding (Interview [Expert 3, 10-06-2020]). For these aspects, AutoML proves a challenge. The technology is still in the developing phase, and the cost aspect is still unknown. While one REDD+ expert mentioned that projects have sufficient funding but the tool should first be implemented at a smaller scale before it should be used at a wider scale (Interview [Expert 5, 26-06-2020]). Two other experts however, commented both that costs are of issue in REDD+, and there is actually limited funding available, financial resources are scarce (Interview [Expert 1 & 5, 2020]).

Another issue is that the technical capabilities of people within local communities could potentially hamper the effectiveness of the classification operation. According to a local community tool developer, the software and overall user-interface should be kept as simple as possible (Corr. Expert 6, 13-07-2020). This would mean that devices are not connected to the internet, and the user interaction within the software is kept at a minimum, with large icons and a limited selection of buttons. A REDD+ expert agreed that the devices used should have very basic functionality, but local communities would definitely have the ability to respond to notifications (Interview [Expert 3, 10-06-2020]). From the interview with a machine learning expert it became clear that the process of image classification is currently mostly done by crowd-sourcing, and it seems from his feedback that there is no real need to integrate local communities in this process (Interview [Expert 2, 09-06-2020]). One social REDD+ expert also mentioned that there is limited internet connectivity with local communities, which are mostly using handheld devices to communicate with the internet (Interview [Expert 3, 10-06-2020]). The limitations of local communities in this aspect make it unlikely that local communities could aid in the classification of images, as this process requires fast internet connection with desktop computer hardware. The lack of local community integration in the model creation however would not mean the model would be less effective, as the model could be kept relatively simple, the kind of image classifications would be limited, and could still be performed by crowd-sourcing as shown by Kaggle (2018).

Based on the information gathered, it is unlikely local communities could easily aid in the classification of satellite imagery. However, in the large scheme of AutoML, image classification is only a small part of the system. In fact, consensus among machine learning experts is that, once the images are classified and the model is created, there is generally no further need for re-training or re-classification of images, unless the model is not performing adequately (Feurer et al. 2015). Overall, this would mean that image classification is an important, but generally not most important part of the AutoML technology implementation. Based on these findings, the involvement of local communities in the system should therefore be seen as that of an end-user, which means limited interaction with data collection.

Overall, before large investments in the tool are made, all experts agree the tool should first be tested at a smaller scale, in for example pilot projects. The costs associated with these projects could then also be compared to the effectivity of the tool. After this assessment, the tool can be further developed.

Transparency of the tool

Experts closely working within REDD+ programs, mention issues with transparency. For example, countries in South-East Asia do not report how they collect data and how they process it (Interview [Expert 4, 11-07-2020]). Technical baseline reports have also been part of the debate around transparent data reporting. One expert mentioned that the used tools are often not mentioned and the way data is collected is also debated (Interview [Expert 5, 26-06-2020]). Both experts mentioned a new tool could provide better and more transparent insights into the deforestation situations (Interview Expert 1 & 5,

2020). An opportunity for the tool could be for “civil society”, which could use a tool like the presented real-time monitoring to provide transparent information about deforestation. Especially in South-East Asia, transparency in REDD+ projects is limited (Interview [Expert 4, 11-07-2020]). An expert with experience in dealing with civil society groups surrounding REDD+ envisions these groups as most promising to put deforestation on the public agenda. However, the expert indicated these groups are limited by the information available, as most countries do not publish their data (Interview [Expert 4, 11-07-2020]). A new monitoring tool, like the one presented, could possibly enable a civil society monitoring solution, which could pressure governments into providing more transparency about deforestation rates (Interview [Expert 4, 11-07-2020]).

Conclusions

The results of the interviews show that AutoML technology has potential within the monitoring system of REDD+. After establishing the technical details, such as the image classification and the use of satellite data, the use-case of the technology could be further defined by the use of value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods. The results show that experts were able to comment and provide feedback with the use of a prototype tool, and that the feedback provided was of use for the future development of AutoML technology in REDD+.

Technical findings of the interviews show that the technology would likely be useful for indigenous people, likely as a tool to monitor their territory. Local communities could potentially have a better overview on changes in their territory and could verify the models' findings with their on-the-ground sampling tools. A second discussed use of the technology would be a tool used by civil society organizations, where the tool would enable a more transparent overview of the changes. A more general use-case was also identified, where (sub)national governments could use the tool to create frequent reports about forest changes, with numerous potential uses for the creation of these more frequent reports, such as new scientific research into forest degradation drivers.

Overall, the AutoML tool seems to have potential for use in REDD+. The experts provided positive feedback and functional remarks that show the technology could play a role in REDD+ monitoring. However, before the technology can be adopted, it still needs to go through several development cycles to further define the details about its implementation. The results of the interviews show that value-sensitive and responsible innovation development methods would be useful to discover and further develop the tool.

6. Discussion

Introduction

In the previous chapter, I presented the results of the expert interviews. In that chapter, a practical use-case of the AutoML technology was discussed. The use-case describes how AutoML technology could be implemented. In this discussion, I will elaborate critically reflect on the results of the expert interviews, the use of the value-sensitive design and responsible innovation methods and give recommendations for future research and use of AutoML technology in REDD+.

AutoML technology is a complex, new technology that uses advanced algorithms. The use of AutoML is a complex research topic. Machine learning in general is often referred to as a “black box” technology, where the underpinnings and the workings of the technology are clouded by the large-scale of technicalities. In this discussion, I will reflect on the ability of value-sensitive design and responsible innovation methods to be used with a black box technology like AutoML. Additionally, I will reflect on the limitations of the study, such as how the set-up of research design could have impacted the results and the impact of future challenges related with the rapid development of AutoML technology.

Research results

In the empirical research chapter, the data gathered from the interviews suggests there is a clear, practical potential use of AutoML technology in REDD+. This potential use-case was also changed compared to the initially conceptualised use-case in the methodology.

The hypothesized use of AutoML, as described in the methodology, was based on information gathered from literature research. Based on the information gathered, a wireframe app was developed which introduced a visual classification system necessary to create an AutoML model. The wireframe app provided a user-interface with options like object detection and additional input variables which are similar to current on-the-ground sampling of forest data. The hypothesised use-case for this app provided a combination of ground sourced data with high-resolution remote sensing data. The AutoML model made with the app-provided data would combine multiple data sources to generate a high level (Tier 3) forest monitoring solution. The functionality of the model and resulting AutoML model were based on current REDD+ monitoring needs as mentioned in scientific literature and guidelines.

The prototype app was introduced to several experts in various fields, who presented feedback regarding several aspects of the apps technical functionality, usefulness in REDD+ and practical (field) implementation. The change from a technical prototype towards the realization of a practical use-case showed a discrepancy between the needs in REDD+, as described in technical documentation, and the actual, practical possibilities of the AutoML technology as determined by experts. This thesis showed that, the processes of value-sensitive design and responsible innovation could be helpful to reflect on the development environment and reduce the discrepancy between theory and practice.

Reflections on expert feedback

One of the limitations of the VSD method related to AutoML, is that the analyses often focus on the external shell built *around* the underlying technology. To give an example of that, for the case of AutoML, the underlying machine learning technology is not an aspect at which most end-users would interact. Most common is the interaction with the GUI, also called graphical user interface. This user interface is the point of interaction for most stakeholders, and also the focus of the value-sensitive design framework (Zhu et al. 2018). The framework’s methods of focus groups and elaborate feedback processes are mostly related to the interaction with the user interface and the functionality of the app (Friedman et al. 2013). The underlying technology of the app could be exchanged with any method. It does not matter whether the app uses machine learning or a more classical form of algorithms, if the app functions in a similar way, the value-sensitive design method does not advise or recommend a specific underlying technological method. It is therefore less useful in determining the actual need for the underlying technology (de Hoop et al. 2016). In this thesis however, more attention was paid to

reflect on questions surrounding the underlying AutoML technology, instead of the GUI and other elements of potential AutoML apps. The results of the thesis show that, even though the VSD method is limited in its scope surrounding the technical background of technology development, in the interviews experts were easily able to connect values and capabilities to those technical details.

The lack of integration from the VSD method for analyzing the underlying technologies, is commonly substituted by the responsible innovation method. With responsible innovation, ethical challenges related to the use of new technologies like machine learning and other forms of AI are an integral part of the development process. The RI method reflects upon the underlying technology used in the software. The value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods are often combined in literature, as they supplement each other in the development process (Owen et al. 2013.)

However, the responsible innovation development method does have its limitations for the use with AutoML. As the AutoML technology is developed and made available by private companies, inherent risks and challenges related to data security and analysis are dependent on the private providers. AutoML and machine learning in general is commonly mentioned in the media, and by the interviewed experts of this thesis, as a “black-box” technology. The underlying algorithms are very complicated and difficult to verify, which means that the way the model is generated is unverifiable by simply looking at the code. With linear regression, there are clear variables that are used for the calculation. With AutoML, these variables are not seen, and there is no method to discover how the model actually works from “the inside”. In the debate around responsible use of machine learning models, the black box notion is often mentioned. There are however several, often not mentioned, considerations that challenge the notion of black-box technology as being less responsible or reliable than classical regression methods. With responsible use of technology as focus of this thesis, I wanted to elaborate on the possibilities of integrating responsible data analysis in AutoML.

The notion of machine learning being a “black box” technology is wide-spread. In popular media and scientific papers, machine learning is described as a black-box due to the inaccessibility to the internal mechanisms which generate results. However, software developers have been working on open-source projects to improve upon the “black-box” characteristics of the technology by introducing various in-depth feedback tools (Github, 2020). With the tools, the inner workings of the model can be visualized and compared with a “classical” linear regression. Comments from software developers indicate the new feedback approach would make AutoML technology more transparent and easier to verify than classical statistical methods (Medium, 2020). The notion of the technology being a “black-box” with the introduction of new feedback methods. At the moment of writing this thesis, these new methods are considered to be still in active development. Therefore, there is very limited scientific study related to these new feedback tools. They are already in a usable state, but it will take time before their development has fleshed out in stable versions which can be deployed in production. Taking this development into account, the importance of regular feedback refraction sessions in the development process, as discussed in the VSD method, are useful for discovering and implementing new innovations like new feedback tools within AutoML.

Challenges with REDD+ project variety

In the research results, a common problem with REDD+ also came forward. REDD+ is an all encompassing term which includes many different countries, projects and types of deforestation prevention. The actual implementation of AutoML technology and the right use-case is dependent on the goal of the REDD+ project. With the large variety of goals and REDD+ implementations, the use-case of AutoML technology would differ throughout REDD+. The value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods do not have guidelines which deal with a large variety of potential projects, instead they are focussed on a single use or project (Lubberink et al. 2017). Therefore, the VSD and RI methods seem most useful for the development of a single use-case of AutoML software within REDD+.

Validation of the research results

The interviews are the basis of the research results, and are supplemented by white-papers and scientific literature. On average, an interview lasted one hour. For each interview, there was a list of questions which discussed specific details related to the specialization of the expert. A limitation in this area is the amount of interviews and the interviewed experts themselves. Ideally, more experts would have been interviewed, as well as other stakeholders like software developers and local communities. In the interviews, there were similar questions repeated for each expert. In the analysis, I compared the answers between experts and drew conclusions from their differences. With more experts, these conclusions might have been more nuanced or would differ. With more general questions, perhaps more general information about machine learning could have been gathered as well. Overall though, the expert opinions were strongly favored towards the results as written down in the research chapter, and I deem it unlikely that, with more expert interviews, the results would have changed much.

Limitations of the research

A large part of the scientific research results were gathered by holding interviews with experts in several domains related to the technology and its application. However, the VSD and RI methods call for more elaborate research methods, such as focus groups, extensive interviews with potential end-users and the build up of personas, power schemes and other methods to determine the right stakeholders and their involvement in the developmental process. Compared to these methods, it's clear that this thesis does not follow the guidelines as described by the methods and as discussed in the conceptual framework. Ideally, I would have interviewed local communities and more stakeholders directly working with REDD+ monitoring. The interviews for local communities would have been focussed less on the technical background, and more, as indicated in the VSD method, on the actual end-user interaction with the tool, such as the GUI. The results of this thesis would probably have been more related to the practical implementation, but also design of the tool for local communities. This would have led to more insight into the design and future development of a specific use-case for that end-user group interviewed. The results gathered with the current group of experts is relevant for a technical analysis of the tool, and with more interviews with the actual end-users, the analysis would have been more detailed with regards to end-user interaction. Overall, I do not expect that the results of this thesis would have changed much, especially considering the highly technical nature of the findings.

Rapid development of AutoML could introduce new features and advancements into various fields discussed in this thesis. Functionality could improve with regards to feedback on model validity and improvements could be made to easier user interfaces. An example of that is the recent introduction (September 2020) of the free-to-use AutoML software by Google, called "Teachable Machine", which introduces a new interface for AutoML built for non-experts, making it even easier to build an AutoML model. As more advancements are made in the domain of AutoML, large software companies might create tools which would aid the development of a monitoring tool for REDD+ in ways unforeseen in this thesis. For example, private companies might produce tools which aid in the creation of machine learning apps, like the prototype wireframe app developed. Such functionality has been part of recent publications by AutoML providers like Google (Google Cloud, 2019).

Recommendations

The development of AutoML is highly dependent on advancements made in software. The use of value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods allow researchers and developers to analyze and reflect upon various themes within the software development process. As a recommendation for future developers of the technology, the possibilities of AutoML discovered in this thesis are based upon developments made by existing providers of AutoML software. It is entirely possible that these tools do not fit the specific use-case of the technology. The available tools are developed for general uses, like image classification. There are, however, also more specialized uses for AutoML, such as the analysis of numerical data and advanced forms of object detection. These possibilities are not yet fully integrated into the software packages available, and require more developer work. In the expert interviews, commentary was given to the current state of AutoML technology, which is still in development. It is possible that, with rapid development of the AutoML technology, new opportunities and possibilities, which are not yet discovered, will be developed. The focus on image classification, as it currently the most realistic option, could be replaced by object detection when the AutoML technology improves. For developers and researchers, regular reflection on the state and development of the technology is thus recommended. The VSD and RI development methods describe these feedback steps in detail.

With improvements in AutoML software, there could be new possibilities developed that are as of yet unexplored in this thesis. For example, better ways to analyze images or numerical data (Google Cloud, 2019). A notable improvement for the use of AutoML for REDD+ would be the ability to combine numerical data with object detection. As of yet, combining two different machine learning models with each other is not possible in AutoML software. The difficulties of combining in numerical data with object detection led to the change in direction with the prototype app, as mentioned earlier in this thesis.

A recommendation for researchers is to pay attention to specific methods in the value-sensitive design method. In this method there is an important place for the use of direct feedback loops and fast iterative processes. With rapid new developments in software, the possibilities of the monitoring tool could potentially be expanded. Without iterative development processes, the monitoring tool developer could miss out on new possibilities with AutoML. Therefore, due to the quickly developing nature of AutoML, in my opinion, it would be advisable to take close regard to the adaptive developing practices of the responsible innovation and value-sensitive design methods.

Techno-optimism with AutoML and REDD+

With new technological development, there is a common notion that the capabilities and possibilities of new technology could improve upon, or solve, societal problems. In the case of this thesis, AutoML was presented as a technological solution for some of the problems in REDD+. AI technologies, like AutoML, have been presented in the media as the next “big thing” in computer technology. The problems they solve however, are still limited in scope, but with an optimistic outlook into the future, computer experts predict AI technology to play a large role in future society.

Future predictions however can be too optimistic. The development of AI technology and AutoML could be slower than predicted and the solutions it brings to REDD+ could potentially be solved with other means. At the current stage of AutoML development, it is likely that the technology would not solve certain issues within REDD+ monitoring as discussed in the introduction. These issues are related to funding, reliability and reporting problems that are inherent to the current software solutions in use within REDD+. The current technical limitations of AutoML technology however make it less useful for solving these issues. Most REDD+ problems seem to exist because of less than ideal funding and stakeholder conflicts. The AutoML technology, in its current form, would likely add an additional monitoring tool, it would not replace one.

With AutoML, a not yet proven technology, wide-spread adoption is therefore unlikely in a short time-frame. However, with the introduction of pilot projects, where the AutoML technology would be tested, the technology would be able to prove itself for its use in, for example, in real-time monitoring.

Conclusion

This chapter reflected on the results of the thesis, its limitations and gave recommendations for future AutoML development. The results of this thesis showed the discrepancy between an initial technological concept and the practical, real-life demands of that technology. The results also showed the many possible use-cases of AutoML technology. Combined with the large variety of projects and monitoring methods used in REDD+, the practical use-case developed was a more simplistic vision of AutoML technology, which would work for multiple scenarios and could be more widely used in REDD+ in general.

Limitations of the thesis were related to the research methodology, which involved interviews with experts. As discussed in the conceptual framework, interviews are only a part of the technological development process. Due to time and general limitations, the interviews taken were with experts working with for example local communities. Ideally however, local communities themselves would be integrated into the research process of this thesis. The results of the thesis would have been more detailed into the actual end-user interaction of the tool, whereas the results are more technical in nature with the current analysis. Another limiting factor is the availability and current development of AutoML software, which is rapidly evolving. New capabilities are added to AutoML software regularly, such as more advanced feedback mechanisms and object detection technologies. The practical use-case developed in the research chapter would possibly be different with a more mature AutoML technology.

In the recommendations part of this discussion, I elaborated on the challenges related to the value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods. These methods describe in general the pathway towards a new software product. They, however, also have limitations. The methods are not targeted with regard to the intricacies of building machine learning software. The value-sensitive design method also does not integrate well with the underlying technological aspects of a new software tool. The addition of responsible innovation is thus essential for this integration. To integrate even more technical aspects into the developmental process, a new method specifically designed for machine learning, called expert-augmented machine learning, could also aid in the development of stakeholder based machine learning monitoring solutions.

Furthermore, the results of this thesis showed that development practices are of importance in the initial phases of the development process. The AutoML prototype app was developed for a specific use-case, and although it could serve multiple other uses, its underlying AutoML technology choice was that of object detection and numerical data analyses. Based on the results of the expert interviews, the underlying AutoML method was adapted towards image classification. When developing new monitoring solutions for REDD+ projects, it's likely that developers face the same issues when creating a new monitoring tool. Even for the initial phases of development, stakeholder involvement is crucial for determining the right direction and thus technological details of AutoML development.

7. Conclusion

REDD+ is one of the ways climate change will be combatted. The success of the program could make a difference for the health of forests and their surrounding ecosystems. The Monitoring, Reporting and Verification processes in REDD+ are essential in achieving the goals of REDD+ projects. These MRV methods primarily use software to detect and monitor deforestation, forest degradation and land-use changes. Recent development in software development have introduced new ways to analyse data, such as satellite data used in MRV processes. With a technology called Automated Machine Learning, data gathered for the MRV processes could be analysed with self-learning statistical methods. However, as AutoML technology has been a recent innovation, limited research has been performed for its viability and potential use in REDD+ MRV processes.

With the rapid development and integration of AutoML in artificial intelligent software in general, future AutoML developments for REDD+ will need to take into account specific REDD+ requirements, such as local community involvement. In this thesis, I researched what the potential use-cases for AutoML technology were in REDD+, potential methods to research AutoML software development, what a prototype application for REDD+ would look like and whether this prototype would generate valuable feedback from experts to be used by the software development methods.

The software development methods identified for AutoML development were value-sensitive design and responsible innovation. Four different software development methods were analyzed, and two of those methods, value-sensitive design and responsible innovation, were chosen as potential methods for researching the future responsible development of AutoML in REDD+. The methods combined ways to research and combine responsible development of a primarily software based tool.

In these methods, the use of stakeholder interviews plays an important role. With stakeholder feedback, several steps within the VSD and RI methods generate data about suitable technological development trajectories. With this data, re-iterative development processes can be followed which would lead to an end-product which is based on extensive stakeholder collaboration and feedback. In this thesis, one of the procedures in both these methods is followed in the form of expert interviews. Following the steps of the software development method experts from several disciplines, connected to the AutoML technology and REDD+, were interviewed about AutoML in REDD+.

To demonstrate the possibilities of AutoML in REDD+, a prototype application was developed. The prototype presented to experts was a mobile application which would use remote sensing satellite data for analysis of deforestation rates, carbon sequestration and overall changes in land-use. With the presentation of the mobile prototype application, feedback was gathered from experts in machine learning and REDD+ with the help of interviews.

The data gathered by these interviews was used to reflect upon the possibility of a single possible use-case of AutoML technology in REDD+. Based on the gathered data, a single, practical use-case of the technology was developed. The use-case was based on reflections of multiple experts upon the prototype application. Experts reflected at first on the technical details of this prototype and it's accompanying use-case, and commented on the difficulties and potential pitfalls of machine learning technology.

Machine learning experts indicated that the practical capabilities of the prototype tool would likely be too complicated in the current early stages of the AutoML technology. They advised that, for a practical implementation of AutoML technology, the first steps of development should be taken with more accessible image classification technologies, without the combination of numerical, ground sampled, data. The data gathered from experts pointed towards a single, practical use-case of AutoML technology in the form of a real-time monitoring system. For this use-case, the AutoML tool would be able to detect changes in the forest and classify these changes based on visual data. To further discuss the possibilities of such a practical use-case, experts in various fields of REDD+ research reflected on the practical uses of a real-time monitoring tool. The experts indicated practical uses for civil society, which has currently limited access to real-time monitoring tools. The AutoML technology could enable non-experts in civil society to pressure or influence public debate with regards to deforestation. A

second potential use of real-time monitoring with AutoML was identified for (sub)national governments. Current monitoring tools use simplified algorithmic methods to differentiate between different types of deforestation. A tool powered by AutoML could potentially classify the type of change detected, which would improve monitoring reliability and effectiveness.

Software development methods, like value-sensitive design and responsible innovation, were successfully used in this thesis to gather data from experts. The results of the interviews show that the methods are capable of successfully gathering data for AutoML technology and develop a realistic use-case for future development. This use-case was initially based on a prototype application, which also showed to be an integral part of the feedback process. In the development process of AutoML technology, frameworks like value-sensitive design and responsible innovation were thus shown to be valuable and beneficial in the developmental process.

The results of this thesis also show that expert feedback should preferably be consulted in the earliest stages of development. Without stakeholder feedback, the development of a tool could shift in a direction which is not suitable for the relevant stakeholders. With rapid development of software, technologies like AutoML will likely become mature and generally implemented in the coming years. With advancements in AutoML, other, more advanced use-cases, which involve more complex data flows and could generate ever more sophisticated models. Ultimately, with AutoML, advanced new data analysis methods could be introduced in REDD+ Monitoring, Reporting and Verification processes. With the ongoing challenges of REDD+ projects and their MRV activities, innovations

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Appendix

Expert	Expertise
1 - Astrid	REDD+ Monitoring
2 - Dario	Machine Learning
3 - Diego	REDD+ Monitoring
4 - Gabrielle	REDD+ (Social/Monitoring)
5 - Bas	REDD+ Monitoring/Social
6 - Gert	Machine Learning
7 - Brenden	UAV expert

In-depth technical look at AutoML

Machine learning is commonly portrayed as a “black box” technology. The algorithms generated by the method can not be manually verified, such as evaluating the formulas used by the algorithm (Feurer et al. 2015). AutoML software developers have therefore put effort into providing tools to verify the accuracy of AutoML models.

In general, the results of the AutoML software are verified by comparing the output of the model with the actual values measured. As discussed in this chapter earlier, AutoML uses a part of the data as “training data”, it optimizes the model to fit the data. The accuracy of the model thus depends on the

Figure 2.9 - Detected label accuracy indicators (Google, 2020)

quality of the data. Verification of the model results is thus an essential step in the model creation process, and there are several methods to verify the accuracy of the model.

Verifying accuracy is an essential part within model creation. As the tool is often used by non-experts, the technical information needs to be presented in such a way, that it is understandable for non-experts and experts alike. To give a few examples of how evaluation is integrated in AutoML, I will demonstrate some of the tools already developed, like those from Google.

An example on how to integrate machine learning evaluation is shown in Figure 2.8. The model determines the type of flower based on a picture. The predicted label is a flower inside an image, like a daisy. The evaluation page of the Google Cloud software now shows the confusion between all the objects inside the image. The confusion matrix could show which of these classifications leads to confusion and needs to be further trained.

Evaluating the statistical model generated with this method requires more in-depth knowledge into statistics, such as R^2 , Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Average Error (MAE). The software could indicate whether these values are in their right margins, and if there's something to be improved upon. The Google Cloud AutoML software package has shown indicators which show whether the model is performing as it should.

In Figure 2.10, the precision of the model is indicated, and further values are shown. Notice the little question marks next to the values, an end-user can click on these values and get more information about the value mentioned. Some of the indicators also have circles which present a visual indication of the quality of that analysis.

Non-experts and AutoML interaction

As AutoML has been developed with non-experts in mind, it would make sense that software design has been adapted for users like those using other applications, like Excel or programs like SPSS. This is however not the case. The non-experts targeted by companies like Google and Microsoft already have experience with other tools like Excel or other programmers that require a higher level of competency in the field of computing, end-users without a set of skills related to computer software would likely find the user-interfaces too complicated.

Non-experts, with no experience in statistics or data analysis are currently not taken into consideration with the user-interface design of the AutoML tools available today.

Image classification vs object detection models

Figure 2.11 - Choice between AutoML models in Google Cloud (Google Cloud, 2020)

AutoML could create image classification or object detection models, in Figure 2.11, the choice between these options is clearly depicted in the graphical user-interface of the AutoML software. An object detection model is designed for general detection of large changes happening in an image. In comparison, an object detection model would have a comprehensive understanding of soil types, vegetation, industry factors and more. The model would be able to generate accurate

results for each type of environment. Such a model would likely generate higher quality results than current remote sensing based models, but would also require the use of big data sets to gather enough data for every region. The choice for an object detection model would likely result in higher set-up costs, but ultimately would provide higher quality analyses.

With a multi-label image classification model, the image itself is analyzed for general information about the objects inside the image. However the objects themselves are not identified. With this method, it is for example not possible to calculate the number of objects in an image. The model would only predict the object is “there” but not it’s size, number or other properties. The creation of an image classification model however requires less detailed data and is easier to verify and evaluate.

Applying value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods upon the research results

The new use-case developed provides a general possibility for the use of the technology in REDD+. However, there many other potential use-cases of the technology. These use-cases and the actual implementation of the technology could be developed with the use of value-sensitive and responsible development methods. This applied analysis is build up around the steps necessary to build a machine learning model, starting with data collection, processing and model creation. The analysis is based on the results of the interviews, scientific research and white-papers, and provides a synthesized overview of this thesis' findings directly translated upon the value-sensitive and responsible innovation methods. The information in this chapter is intended for future developers and policy makers who want to see an applied version of a VSD and RI method. In this synthesized analysis, the VSD and RI methods are applied to specific parts of the VSD development process, such as stakeholder analysis, value integration and stage-gate criteria.

Stakeholder analysis

The first step in the value-sensitive design method is to determine the direct and indirect stakeholders with regard to data collection. Indirect stakeholders would not interact with the AutoML technology, but would experience the results from it’s use. For example, local community members who get financial benefits as a result from the AutoML analysis, or civilians concerned about ethical questions surrounding the use of machine learning in REDD+. A direct stakeholder will have interaction with the AutoML software. This could for example be persons performing image classification, capturing high resolution remote sensing data or programmers.

Most stakeholders can be categorized as direct or indirect. However, there might be stakeholders that are both indirect and direct stakeholders. For example, a local community member might help to capture remote sensing data with drones, and also live in the affected area. The distinction of stakeholders is often connected to the power level they have. For example, a local community member living in a protected forest could be an indirect stakeholder. The member does not use the developed software, but the software does affect the stakeholder’s environment.

With the stakeholder analysis, the goal is to determine the important stakeholders involved with the data collection process. For the use-case of this thesis, whereby satellite monitoring is used, a stakeholder could be the private company providing the satellite images and forest organizations who purchase the data. In a different use-case, for example, the use of UAV’s, stakeholders could be local community members operating the equipment, UAV suppliers and UAV software developers.

Between these stakeholders, the VSD method describes the importance of power structures. From power structures, conflicts may arise. It is therefore important to map out and determine all involved stakeholders within the data collection process, their power levels and expectations.

During the data collection process, there are several steps that can be taken to improve the quality of development. One method is the use of reflexive processes, in which continuous feedback is given throughout the development process. A public debate could be held with relevant stakeholders, both direct and indirect, to discover potential problems with the data collection process of AutoML in REDD+.

Value integration

With the use of interviews and data collection, the important values for the development of the tool should be determined. For the use-case of AutoML, these values could change the choice of data collection method. In this thesis, the values of reliability, efficiency and effectiveness led to the

choice of satellite imagery. However, with a different set of values, this choice could be different. The values depend on the goal of the system, what the system should achieve and what is demanded by all relevant stakeholders. For example, if from the stakeholder analysis comes forward the monitoring tool should provide as detailed information as possible.

Responsible model creation

AutoML models can be created with the use of internet platforms or local software. There are many suppliers of cloud-based user friendly interfaces. Based on expert feedback however, these platforms can be limiting in their capabilities, and create a dependency on the platform. This generates many issues surrounding the safety of data, ease of use and future possibilities with the data gathered. Because the use-case of the specialized use-case, offline and open-source platforms would provide a more transparent development of the model. These offline platforms are however still in development and lack the feature-set of the cloud-based alternatives.

AutoML products, such as Google, Microsoft and IBM. These companies have pre-configured and

There are several use-cases of AutoML technology in REDD+. No matter what use-case, every AutoML implementation will face similar issues and problems based on the nature of machine learning models. Based on expert feedback, I have developed a few key methods to deal with some of the typical AutoML drawbacks. Machine learning models are often referred to as "black boxes", where the output is simply given without feedback as to how this output came to be. AutoML tools contain several

indicators which show the performance and quality of the model. This allows non-experts to build AutoML models. It also allows for easier integration into existing data analysis platforms.

Fulfilling stage-gate criteria

1. Risks identified, manageable and deemed acceptable

For AutoML, this would mean that the risks associated with its implementation are identified, manageable and deemed acceptable. The first challenge is to identify the actual risks. Identifying risks could be done using literature research or expert interviews. With “normal” machine learning, there are already many identified risks. Automated machine learning uses new methods to lower these risks for non-experts (Feurer et al. 2015). It is essential these methods are used during the analysis with AutoML.

2. Compliant with relevant regulations

There are monitoring guidelines from the UNFCCC which describe technical details on how to set-up monitoring for REDD+. The AutoML technology will have to be compliant with the existing monitoring guidelines of the UNFCCC, and those of national governments.

3. Clear communication

A large challenge when introducing new technology is the creation of documentation. Without proper documentation, mistakes could be made and wrong analyses could be performed. It is the responsibility of the producer of the AutoML tool to produce the right documentation.

4. Applications and impacts described and mechanisms put in place to review these

After implementing the AutoML technology, there should be certain mechanisms in place to review the impact of the technology. For example, by taking into account the results from the persona stakeholder analysis and determined hazards.

5. Mechanisms identified to understand public and stakeholder views

This last stage is important to identify the ethical considerations of stakeholders. In the value-sensitive design framework, this is already an important part of the method. Stilgoe et al. (2014) describe a combination of stakeholder mapping exercises and interviews to get an overview of different stakeholder views. These views give an indication into the ethical considerations of stakeholders. For example, maybe public views on the use of machine learning are negative because of mis-use of data, this public view will then need to be identified and can be used to improve the tool or technology.